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DISSERTATION

Role of Generative AI and Factors Affecting Financial Performance of SMEs in Southeast Asia

By

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Abstract

Small to medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are becoming more exposed to Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI), but most of them are unable to translate adoption into financial benefits. Although previous studies demonstrate the potential usefulness of AI, there is little empirical information as to why GenAI can provide value to the SMEs and under what circumstances effective adoption can be achieved. This paper examines the association between the GenAI adoption and the SME financial performance and the role played by the organizational and environmental factors. Based on a resource orchestration perspective and Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) framework, the paper explores human capabilities, technological capabilities, funding capital and market factors. A mixed method sequential explanatory methodology was used. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was used to analyze quantitative survey data, after which, qualitative interviews were conducted. The results indicate that there is a strong positive correlation between GenAI adoption and financial performance. Funding capital emerged as the strongest direct predictor of GenAI adoption, followed by market pressure. However, qualitative findings show that these factors should not be interpreted as independent parallel drivers. Instead, GenAI adoption in Southeast Asian SMEs is better understood as a sequenced and conditional decision-making process, where SMEs respond to a trigger, commit resources and then activate human and technological capabilities at different stages of implementation. The findings suggest that GenAI can create financial value for SMEs, but not through technological sophistication alone. Rather, it is realized through disciplined resource orchestration, proportionate investment and effective execution under real operating constraints.

Keywords: Generative AI, SMEs, financial performance, new technology adoption

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The emergence of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) represents a transformative shift in the technological landscape for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), particularly in the rapidly evolving economies of Southeast Asia (Dwivedi et al., 2023; Iyelolu et al., 2024). In the past, big companies with established technological infrastructure were the first to make AI adoption (Raisch and Krakowski, 2021), but GenAI has reduced the entry barrier of smaller businesses with straightforward and affordable solutions that can be scaled (Mangifera et al., 2023). These tools can influence various business processes, such as customer interaction and predictive analytics and internal process automation, by improving data-based decision-making, decreasing the number of manual tasks, and creating content on a large scale (Gupta, 2024; Scaria and Sengottaiyan, 2025).

Over 95% of all businesses are SMEs, and they provide a great contribution to employment and GDP in the ASEAN countries (OECD, 2021; World Bank, 2020). However, all these are usually met with continuous obstacles including low levels of digital maturity, lack of abilities, and restricted access to finances, which slow down the process of technology diffusion (ADB, 2022; Asian Development Bank, 2022). Consequently, the area is a distinctive and unexplored prospect to comprehend the factors and effects of GenAI implementation among smaller companies.

Current studies indicate that the digital transformation in SMEs is determined by both the availability of technology and the organizational preparedness as well as environmental factors (Badghish and Soomro, 2024; Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990). Research based on the Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) model has also

found an array of enabling and constraining conditions such as workforce capabilities, technological infrastructure, market pressures along with access to capital that, in combination, have a collective effect on the rate and success of adoption (Iyelolu et al., 2024; Paetz, 2023).

However, the current interest in GenAI notwithstanding, the use of the technology in SMEs is scarcely studied, especially regarding financial and operational performance (Dwivedi et al., 2023; Ayankoya et al., 2025). A significant portion of scholarly literature either conceives GenAI adoption as a dichotomy or does not draw a line between conventional machine learning applications and generative tools that can process natural language, create images and make autonomous decisions.

The paper addresses this research gap and uncovers practical and implementable insights by exploring how adopting GenAI will financially and operationally affect the Southeast Asian SMEs through a mixed methods approach. By developing the model upon a conceptual framework based on Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE), it is expanded to practical and actionable deliverables, by incorporating human, technological, financial, and market issues as facilitators of adoption. The study examines how GenAI adoption connects contextual conditions to performance outcomes providing a more refined, capability-dependent perspective of the impact of technology for SMEs in Southeast Asia.

The results contribute both theoretically and practically. In theory, this study can explain the channels by which GenAI can generate business value in the SME setting. In practice, it educates policy makers, vendors of technology and leaders of SMEs on how to take actions to realize the potential of GenAI.

1.1 Background and Context

Economies across Southeast Asia rely on SMEs to function, with approximately ninety per cent of all firms in each country registered classified as SMEs (World Bank, 2020). Over fifty percent of their employment can be attributed to SMEs (OECD, 2021; World Bank, 2020). Emerging economies generally rely on the SMEs more than the mature economies in Southeast Asia (OECD, 2021; Rahman, 2024). Although SMEs are important cornerstones of Southeast Asian economies, they are often constrained by a lack of financial resources, management capacity, and access to capital.

However, recent advances in computing power have changed the landscape with the maturation of AI (Sánchez et al., 2025). This has changed the way firms operate and leverage technology (Ines et al., 2024). New empirical data shows implementation of AI has the potential to improve SME performance through improving forecast accuracy, data-driven decision making (Ayankoya et al., 2025), cash flow management and operational efficiency (Ines et al., 2024).

Other recent developments indicate AI-supported financial decision-making can improve short-term efficiency, and long-term economic resilience (Begum, 2025). Benefit magnitude varies among firms, sectors and institutional settings (Dwivedi et al., 2023; McKinsey Global Institute, 2023). While large firms are traditionally first to adopt new technologies (Gamage et al., 2020; Rajaram et al., 2024), SMEs encounter significant obstacles (Raisch and Krakowski, 2021). Among the challenges include a lack of digital preparedness, skills gaps, data quality issues, financial limitations, and uncertainty about the payback (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Iyelolu et al., 2024). These have made the implementation of AI lag among SMEs, ensuring the performance implications of AI are not fully realized. New data therefore indicate blind use of AI does

not necessarily lead to better performance (Ayinaddis, 2025; Badghish & Soomro, 2023).

Instead, performance uplift is conditional on integration of AI into the functioning of the organization, decision-making processes, and management (Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024). The proposed study is placed in this changing landscape and aims to investigate the connection between the adoption of AI and the performance of SMEs in terms of financial results with the help of a mixed-methods approach.

The study combines quantitative and qualitative knowledge of SME leaders and is not limited to superficial metrics of adoption. It is hoped this study will help to gain a more profound idea of how and why AI can lead to better performance in SMEs.

1.2 Problem Statement

Although there is increasing scholarly, and policy interest in the adoption of AI by SMEs, unresolved issues remain. Beginning with a focus on the determinants of AI adoption and not performance impacts little is known regarding the relationship between AI adoption and the achievement of quantifiable financial returns (Badghish & Soomro, 2024).

Second, quantitative studies often provide statistically significant relationships in the field of AI adoption, and its performance but do not explain the mechanisms that underlie these correlations (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Shahadat et al., 2023). Recent studies recommend mixed-methods to reveal the role of organizational context, managerial cognition, and development of capability in creating AI-enabled outcomes (Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024; Lu et al., 2022).

Finally, studies focus on particular geographies or individual industries, obscuring application to the SME context. As a result, there is a gap in how SME business leaders

understand GenAI implementations and its effects on financial performance of their SMEs organizations, how such effects are mediated through the organizational conditions and environmental factors (Badghish & Soomro, 2024). It is critical to seal this understanding gap so that technological progress for SMEs can be leveled in the region (Rahman, 2024; Rajaram et al., 2024).

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to develop the connection between the use of Generative AI and the financial performance of SMEs in Southeast Asia, and the empowering conditions that affect the realization of the value used. This development will be adopted to create an applied contribution to the growing demands of practical GenAI adoption strategies within SMEs (Gupta, 2024; Mariani and Dwivedi, 2024; OECD, 2023), and four main area domains are the human capabilities (Benitez et al., 2024), technological infrastructure (Ayinaddis, 2024; Barkley et al., 2024), financial resources (Arranz et al., 2023; Barkley et al., 2024) and market factors (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Iyelolu et al., 2024).

These aspects have been identified as being critical in determining the probability of adopting as well as the efficacy of AI use (Gupta, 2024). Southeast Asia can be viewed as a rather pertinent setting to this question. The share of SMEs in enterprises in the region is more than 97 percent and is a significant contributor to the national GDP (World Bank, 2020; OECD, 2021). With the renewed efforts by governments and technology providers to shift to the digital era, exploring how SMEs use these new tools is becoming a critical concern, to both the regional innovation and competitiveness (Rahman, 2024).

Although most SMEs, in particular the ones that are predominant in Southeast Asia, are keen to implement emerging technologies, they usually experience a high level of

uncertainty regarding the starting point, how to prepare their teams, or what outcomes to expect in the realistic sense (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Badghish & Soomro, 2024). As an example, an SME can deploy a generative chatbot or price-generating AI without the internal data structure or the necessary staff expertise to achieve full value that can lead to unimpressive returns or pilot failures (Iyelolu et al., 2024).

This study offers a context-specific and practice-based view of these issues. The study is grounded in Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) (Hughes et al. 2025; Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990), an established framework in applied innovation research particularly in the adoption of new technology (Hughes et al. 2025; Paetz, 2023). Whereas the traditional models only look at the triggers of adoption, this study further extends it to the outcome of financial performance, linking it to the elements of TOE which is a gap that is continuously gaining prominence both in academic and practitioner literature (Mangifera et al., 2023; Mariani and Dwivedi, 2024).

It encompasses a mixed methods approach where a quantitative model based on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) is used alongside qualitative thematic analysis of the experience of SME leaders (Ayinaddis, 2025; Dwivedi et al., 2023). This allows viewing GenAI adoption in a broad context and in what circumstances and how it leads to quantifiable results in SMEs in Southeast Asia.

1.4 Research Questions

The research aims to build understanding of how and under what conditions GenAI impacts and delivers value for SMEs in Southeast Asia. While progressing the aim, a measurable link between GenAI adoption and financial performance first needs to be established. Then, grounded in prior research, factors such as people, technological

readiness, funding, and market conditions, are probed to determine how they shape this link and help make GenAI adoption more effective. Finally, the link is validated as depth is added by capturing how SME leaders themselves elaborate on success factors.

The sequence of the research questions is intentional. RQ1 first examines the contextual conditions that shape GenAI adoption, because without understanding these human, technological, financial, and market factors, the performance relationship cannot be interpreted meaningfully. RQ2 then adds qualitative depth by exploring how SME leaders experience these conditions as pathways, barriers, and enablers in practice. RQ3 finally assesses the financial performance relationship once the conditions and pathways of adoption have been established.

This study is guided by the Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) framework and a resource orchestration perspective. The TOE framework helps explain how technological, organizational, and environmental conditions shape GenAI adoption in SMEs. The resource orchestration perspective complements this by explaining how SMEs organize limited human, technological, and financial resources to turn adoption into business value. This framing is introduced here in Chapter 1 which is further developed in Chapter 2 and operationalized in Chapter 3.

The research questions are as follows:

RQ1: How do human capabilities, technological capabilities, financial resources, and market dynamics shape the relationship between Generative AI adoption and SME financial performance?

RQ2: What themes emerge from SME leaders' experiences that explain the pathways, barriers, and enabling conditions for translating Generative AI adoption into financial value?

RQ3: What is the relationship between Generative AI adoption and financial performance among SMEs in Southeast Asia?

1.5 Significance of the Study

The overwhelming majority of businesses in Southeast Asia are SMEs: more than 97 percent throughout the region and up to 45 percent of GDP and 70 percent of total employment in the ASEAN member countries (OECD, 2021; World Bank, 2020). In Singapore, 99 percent of all businesses are SMEs, contributing 99 percent of GDP, and over 70 percent of the workforce is employed by SMEs (Department of Statistics Singapore, 2025). Understanding how technological transformation such as Generative AI affects most of Singapore's value creation therefore cannot be ignored.

Resource constraints persist through technological and innovation cycles. Where larger firms may have capacity to absorb and experiment with GenAI (Badghish & Soomro, 2024), SMEs seem to be left with vague directions to adoption and lack the resources to achieve business value (Lu et al., 2022). Moreover, commensurate with the size of their investment, larger firms have greater impact on the direction of AI experimentation, whereas SMEs work on smaller capital bases (Arranz et al., 2023; Barkley et al., 2024), less advanced infrastructure (Ayinaddis, 2024), and limited inside potentials (Benitez et al., 2024). These characteristics compound to cause an inequitable gap: where some firms proceed to the next stage of high-impact AI applications, others stagnate (Iyelolu et al., 2024).

Therefore, this research is important so that SMEs might become equipped to bridge the gap. If the drivers of GenAI value creation can be unearthed, how, and under what circumstances it assists SMEs to generate more value (Ayankoya et al., 2025;

Badghish and Soomro, 2024) per capita spend, then this gap may shrink. Broadly, the research adds to the discussion of digital inclusion since the use of AI is not yet a uniform distribution amongst firms or regions (OECD, 2023; Paetz, 2023).

Just as the adoption and exploitation of the Internet, particularly through the use of e-commerce, had the effect of enhancing SME competitiveness and reach, adoption of GenAI is having a similar effect (Dwivedi et al., 2023; Gupta, 2024). Understanding SME adoption of these tools assists in developing effective digital inclusion strategies, shaping the policy of the state, and influencing the support mechanisms of the private sector in the region (Mariani & Dwivedi, 2024; McKinsey Global Institute, 2023; Rahman, 2024). The given study can bridge that gap by narrowing down to the concept of Southeast Asian SMEs and providing them with a voice in the context of GenAI adoption as an implemented practice (Iyelolu et al., 2024; Ayinaddis, 2025).

1.6 Contributions

The paper contributes to scholarly literature and practice in several ways. First, it will broaden the use of the TOE framework by relating the adoption enablers to not only the adoption act, but also quantifiable financial performance outcomes, which is a topic that is relatively underexplored, particularly in SME settings (Paetz, 2023; Badghish & Soomro, 2024).

Second, it introduces a Southeast Asian prism to a research field that has traditionally been dominated by western enterprise case studies, with an offering of insights that are localized due to the economic and online reality of the region (OECD, 2023; Rahman, 2024).

Third, the research is based on mixed methods, which involves combining qualitative views of SME leaders with quantitative structural modeling. This will enable a

better comprehension of not only the existence of the working of GenAI in SMEs but also how and why it succeeds or fails in various SME settings (Dwivedi et al., 2023; Ayinaddis, 2025).

Fourth, the research provides a feasible diagnostic, which can be used in policy design, vendor support, and the leadership of SMEs in terms of AI adoption by emphasizing barriers, enabling conditions, and performance impact (OECD, 2021).

Lastly, the study to deliver a practical decision-making tool for SME leaders in Southeast Asia by translating the findings into a structured adoption model that can guide whether, when and how GenAI should be implemented in practice. Rather than treating GenAI adoption as a generic digital initiative, this will help SME leaders to assess strategic necessity, resource commitment and organizational readiness in a disciplined and sequenced manner beyond conceptual insights.

1.7 Motivation

The motivation behind this research comes from observing a growing disconnect between the accelerating hype around GenAI, and the many SMEs who are still unsure how to engage with it meaningfully to be effective (Rajaram et al., 2024).

Having worked closely with SMEs in technology advisory and transformation roles, the author has seen firsthand how leaders are often eager but overwhelmed. They want to explore AI, but face a minefield of unclear costs, steep learning curves, and limited technical capacity (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Iyelolu et al., 2024).

For now, the Southeast Asian region is at a digital crossroads: governments are pushing national AI strategies, digital economy frameworks, and SME support policies, but adoption remains uneven (OECD, 2021; Mariani & Dwivedi, 2024). A real risk of un-inclusive innovation remains (McKinsey, 2023; OECD, 2023). This study, then, is

motivated by the drive to close that gap by providing grounded, evidence-based insights that help SMEs, policymakers, and ecosystem players understand not just what GenAI is, but what it takes for it to work in practice.

1.8 Scope, Limitations, and Assumptions

This section outlines the boundaries and parameters within which the study was conducted alongside the limitations and assumptions. This helps to ensure transparency in the study's applicability, reliability, and generalizability.

Scope

This research concerns the financial- and operational performance of SMEs in southeast Asia that have or are currently implementing GenAI tools. The research does not consider big firms, or SMEs from regions outside of southeast Asia, and neither does it assess technical performance of general AI. Rather, it focuses on organizational level adoption and the financial result potentially attributable to that adoption.

Limitations

As in other SME research studies (Gupta, 2024; Rajaram et al., 2024), this study relies on self-reported measurements of GenAI adoption, financial performance, and the proportion of financial performance that the SME considers to be attributed to that GenAI adoption. SMEs seldom have audited financial data (Shahadat et al., 2023), and it is unlikely SMEs will have sophisticated firm-level studies to measure impact (Gupta, 2024; Wonglimpiyarat, 2015). These are likely to limit the study's reliability. It was determined that cross-sectional research design is restrictive to identifying the causal factors, since adoption effects are recorded at a particular time.

Assumptions

Respondents are expected to have sufficient knowledge about their firm to evaluate the use of GenAI, and financial performance correctly (Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024). The study also assumes that perceived financial performance reflects actual performance trends.

1.9 Thesis Structure

This thesis is organized into six chapters:

- **Chapter 1** introduces the study, explains why it matters, outlines the research questions, and frames the study using TOE model. It also sets out the scope, motivation, and contributions of the research.
- **Chapter 2** reviews the existing literature on GenAI, SME digital adoption, and business performance. It identifies gaps and builds the conceptual framework used to guide the study and develop the hypotheses.
- **Chapter 3** describes the research design. It explains the mixed-methods approach, data collection, and how both the quantitative and qualitative phases were carried out.
- **Chapter 4** presents the findings. It covers the results of the quantitative analysis (PLS-SEM), the qualitative themes from SME interviews, and how both parts come together to answer the research questions.
- **Chapter 5** discusses the results in detail. It links the findings back to the research questions and hypotheses and shows how they compare them with prior studies.
- **Chapter 6** concludes the thesis. It summarizes what was learned, what it means for theory and practice, and what future research can explore.

Each chapter builds on the last to give a complete view of how GenAI adoption

plays out in real-world SME settings and what factors shape its impact.

1.10 Chapter Summary

The chapter has formed the basis of the study by defining the relevance of SMEs within the economic landscape of Southeast Asia, and the increased relevance of Generative AI as a disruptive technology. The identified gap in the research is the lack of knowledge in assessing the impact of GenAI adoption on financial performance in different organizations and in different organizational and environmental contexts. Aligned along with the strong relevant significance of the study and timeliness of the study, this research is driven by the strong motivation to provide reinforcement and fresh insights across to practitioners from policy makers to SME decision makers.

The approach of mixed methods adopted to investigate the five hypotheses and three core research questions is also anchored in relevant topics surfaced across multiple literature (Gupta, 2024). The next chapter will review the relevant theoretical and empirical literature to position the study within existing academic discourse and support the development of the study's conceptual framework.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

The chapter reviews the current state of research relating to GenAI adoption and the enabling factors that affect the financial performance outcome. The theoretical grounding of the study is based on Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) framework.

The chapter is structured to build the case up from general themes in GenAI adoption, to specific mediating factors such as human factors, technological infrastructure, market forces as well as funding capital. It also sets up the conceptual framework which leads to the hypotheses that will later be tested in this study.

2.1 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to critically analyze and synthesize the available scholarly research that is applicable to the adoption of Generative Artificial Intelligence and its effects on financial performance of small and medium sized enterprises (Dwivedi et al., 2023; Eze Ijeoma et al., 2025). In addition to summarizing the previous studies, the chapter seeks to build theory as it allows assessing opposing positions, determining trends and contradictions in the existing empirical data, and deriving the hypotheses used in the current investigation in a systematic manner (Ayinaddis, 2025; Badghish & Soomro, 2024). More recent regional research also underscores the situation that relevance and impact of Generative AI adoption are very contextual (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Rahman, 2024), and in particular those developing and emerging SME ecosystems like those in Southeast Asia. The empirical and bibliometric evidence (Ayinaddis, 2025) suggests that Southeast Asian SMEs continue to be plagued by the problem of financial literacy, access

to capital (Rahman, 2024), uneven digital maturity that precondition the process of adopting digital technologies and, consequently, the outcome of the following financial performance (Sunandes et al., 2025).

Case-based studies in Singapore (Chua, 2025), Malaysia (Rahman, 2024), and Indonesia (Rajaram et al., 2024) also confirm that although AI tools have the potential of providing tangible operational benefits, the adoption process heavily depends on firm-level preparedness, system integration, and employee acceptance (Chua, 2025). These results support the idea of a context-specific synthesis of the literature that considers regional structural limitations and firm-specific capabilities (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Gupta, 2024). The rise of Generative AI has also caused the research focus to shift away from AI as a technology to enhance productivity, and instead, focus on AI as a cognitive and strategic ability that can help in managerial judgment, prediction and decision quality (Dwivedi et al., 2023; Gupta, 2024; Raisch & Krakowski, 2021).

Research continues to indicate that the benefits of Generative AI in the case of SMEs are not only in the revenues of automation (Raisch and Krakowski, 2021), but also in the fact that it can support financial planning, scenario analysis, or even the emergence of new business market opportunities, which would otherwise remain concealed (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Ines et al., 2024).

The literature is still disjointed in various streams of research despite this increased literature (Arranz et al., 2023). The literature on AI adoption usually focuses on antecedent factors like technological preparedness (Barkley et al., 2024), or organizational assets (Benitez et al. 2024) or environmental pressure (Arranz et al., 2023) and does so independently, even though these variables typically work together (Ayinaddis, 2025; Iyelolu et al., 2024). Conversely, research on the results of firm performance often base

interpretation on AI adoption as a blanket intervention without giving enough attention to contextual factors that influence its performance (Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024; Eze Ijeoma et al., 2025).

Such a division has restricted the emergence of integrative explanations of the interaction between AI adoption and firm level capabilities and external conditions on the result of the financial performance in SMEs (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Badghish & Soomro, 2024). This gap is especially important because AI is not the first technology to be adopted with strong expectations of disruption before clear and direct empirical evidence of realized firm-level results is established. As with earlier waves of enterprise technology, firms may invest heavily in implementation long before actual value creation is fully understood. To overcome these shortcomings, this literature review is organized by a capability and context sensitive framework based on Technology Organization Environment perspective (Eze Ijeoma et al., 2025; Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990). TOE has been extensively used to analyze the effects of technology, organizational capabilities, and environmental pressures on innovation decisions separately and their joint impact on innovations in SMEs (Ayinaddis, 2025), as it enables the consideration of the three factors together (Gupta, 2024).

Recent research, however, claims TOE as an inadequate performance outcome determinant (Hugh et al., 2025) unless it is further prolonged with firm level capabilities and financial constraints that moderate the value realization (Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024; Ayinaddis, 2025; Block et al., 2021). In line with this school of thought, the current research (Hugh et al., 2025) has conceptualized the adoption of the Generative AI as a key enabling capability whose performance effects are dependent on four areas that are interrelated, namely, human capabilities (Gupta, 2024), technological capabilities (Barkley

et al., 2024), funding capital, and market factors (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Iyelolu et al., 2024). Conceptually, this also raises the possibility that GenAI value realization may be strongest not when any one factor is considered in isolation, but when these four conditions are sufficiently aligned. In other words, there may be a practical zone of convergence in which the four factors reinforce one another and increase the likelihood that GenAI adoption translates to meaningful financial and operational outcomes.

Managerial skills, learning capacity, and AI-related expertise are also human capabilities that affect the proper usage of Generative AI tools (Ines et al., 2024; Kraus et al., 2021). The technological capabilities will represent the quality of data infrastructure, integration of the systems, and scalability needed to deploy AI (Benitez et al., 2024; Lu et al., 2022). Funding capital constitutes the finances that will be required to invest in AI technologies and absorb risks in relation to them (World Bank, 2020). Market factors include the level of rivalry, customer anticipations, and industry forces that dictate adoption incentive and strategic relevance (Autio et al., 2021; OECD, 2023).

Financial performance is considered as a multidimensional outcome, that is, it contains both the indicators of economy like revenue growth and profitability, as well operational indicators like efficiency, the quality of decisions and resilience (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Eze Ijeoma et al., 2025). This interest is consistent with the current attention in the literature to shift the discussion about adoption measures and focus on the real business value of AI in SMEs (Badghish & Soomro, 2023; Mangifera et al., 2023). Based on this, the chapter reviews the literature in the interconnected thematic areas that indicate the proposed conceptual framework. It starts analyzing the history of artificial intelligence and Generative AI in the organizational and decision-making situations (Dwivedi et al., 2023; Raisch and Krakowski, 2021).

The chapter subsequently examines empirical studies on the adoption of AI in SMEs, including the adoption barriers and structural limitations (Ayinaddis, 2025; Iyelolu et al., 2024). This chapter then examines the Technology-Organization-Environment model and its developments in AI adoption studies (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990). A review of literature on the results of financial performance in SMEs is then conducted (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Eze Ijeoma et al., 2025). Lastly, these streams are combined to build a consistent conceptual base informing the hypotheses and methodological framework of the study (Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024; Gupta, 2024).

This chapter will go further than the descriptive summarization that is implemented by other scholars in their literature review and gives a theory-based synthesis that explains how the use of the proposed conceptual model of Generative AI adoption, in association with organizational and environmental capabilities, leads to financial performance results in the SMEs (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Badghish & Soomro, 2024). By doing this, the chapter has provided a proper theoretical channel through which previous studies have led to the hypotheses formulated in Chapter 1 and further developed throughout Chapter 2.

2.2 Conceptual Framework

The theoretical framework relies mainly on Technology Organization Environment perspective, which has been used extensively in the research of the adoption of digital and artificial intelligence to describe the forces of technology, organization, and environment shape innovation decisions in SMEs (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Shahadat et al., 2023; Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990;). Although a number of papers on TOE based studies have been primarily concerned with the antecedents of adoption, as noted by recent studies, there is a need to expand this view towards post adoption outcomes, especially financial performance, to understand the business value of AI investment in the context of SMEs

(Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024; Ayankoya et al., 2025).

The available literature indicates that the adoption of AI does not have a homogeneous and unconditional impact on the positive performance of firms, but rather a relationship with complementary organizational and environmental factors that determine the level of assimilation and value generation (Ayinaddis, 2025; Badghish & Soomro, 2024). In this respect, the framework includes four contextual domains which indicate these complementary conditions. Figure 1 illustrates this.

Figure 1

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 demonstrates the conceptual framework underpinning this research, showing how the adoption of GenAI impacts financial performance. The framework identifies four contextual factors that shape the conditions under which GenAI adoption occurs and translates into performance outcomes. They are namely human capabilities, technological capabilities, funding capital and market factors. These represent key dimensions from TOE framework and are treated in this study as interrelated conditions rather than isolated drivers. At this stage, this framework also introduces the conceptual possibility that GenAI value realization may be strongest when four conditions are

sufficiently aligned. In other words, there may be a practical zone of convergence where these four factors reinforce one another and increase the likelihood of meaningful financial and operational outcomes.

Table 1 presents the core constructs stated in the conceptual framework and supporting academic literature.

Table 1

Constructs and Supporting Literature

Construct	Role in Framework	Key References
Generative AI Adoption	Adoption and use of GenAI tools	Ayinaddis (2025); Dwivedi et al. (2023); Iyelolu et al. (2024); Mangifera et al. (2023); Badghish & Soomro (2024); Hugh et al. (2025)
Human Capabilities	Staff digital skills and organizational learning culture that support GenAI integration.	Benitez et al. (2024); Abdul Wahab & Radmehr (2024); Ayankoya et al. (2025); Hughes et al. (2025); Rajaram et al. (2024)
Technological Capabilities	Existing digital and IT infrastructure.	Barkley et al. (2024); Ayinaddis (2024); Shahadat et al. (2023); Paetz (2023); De Mattos et al. (2023)
Funding Capital	Availability of financial resources for training and experimentation.	Barkley et al. (2024); Arranz et al. (2023); Shahadat et al. (2023); Chakraborty et al. (2025)
Market Factors	External competitive pressure, customer expectations.	Bresciani et al. (2021); Rahman (2024); Chatterjee et al. (2023); Flaminiano (2025)
Financial Performance	Financial outcomes such as revenue, profitability and cost savings.	Iyelolu et al. (2024); Mangifera et al. (2023); Rajaram et al. (2024); Ayinaddis (2025)

Table 1 showed each construct is paired with its specific role in the framework and a curated list of key references that illustrates its theoretical and empirical grounding. This forms the foundation for the development of the research's hypothesis, as it is derived from current studies across GenAI adoption and SME performance.

2.3 Generative AI and AI Adoption in SMEs

The adoption of artificial intelligence is a significantly more prevalent topic in the research of SMEs because it is expected to improve decision making, productivity, and competitiveness in resource limited settings (Ayinaddis, 2025; Lu et al., 2022). The difference between SMEs and large enterprises in adopting digital technologies is in the fact that their adoption is usually constrained by the factors of financial resources, managerial capacity, and technological infrastructure, which influence the rate and level of AI adoption (Kindström et al., 2022; OECD, 2021). Consequently, adoption of AI in SMEs is not a scaled down adoption of AI in large firms but is a phenomenon that needs place-based analysis (Badghish & Soomro, 2023; Mangifera et al., 2023).

Newer sources (Barkley et al., 2024) point at the transition to sophisticated AI systems based on augmentation over human decision making (Dwivedi et al., 2023; Raisch & Krakowski, 2021). This change applies especially to SMEs, where the decision-making process of the management is often centralized and depends crucially on the choice taken by only a few crucial individuals (Ines et al., 2024; Kraus et al., 2021). These features distinguish between Generative AI and the previous digital technologies and place it as a possible strategic enabler instead of an operational one (Gupta, 2024; Mariani & Dwivedi, 2024).

It is also emphasized in the literature that AI adoption in SMEs is often reactive and not proactive (Drydakis, 2022), because of competition pressure, customer demands (Arranz et al., 2023) or external shocks, like the COVID 19 pandemic (Lu et al., 2022). Research by post-pandemic (Lu et al., 2022) shows that SMEs are starting to regard AI implementation as a vulnerability coping mechanism, better forecasting (Begum, 2025), and reduced operational disturbances (Autio et al., 2021). Nonetheless, such a reactive

orientation typically leads to short term adoption choices that cannot be backed by long term capability development (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Kindström et al., 2022).

Nevertheless, the ascent of the technology is also associated with limitations to aggressive adoption (Chua, 2025) as the nascent nature of the technology does not necessarily bring corresponding rewards and a company should always ensure that it does not over experiment (Benitez et al., 2024). The other theme that runs across the literature is the difference between the adoption and the assimilation of AI (Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024). Whereas adoption explains the first step of adopting AI technologies, assimilation describes the degree to which AI has been integrated into the organizational processes and decision routines (Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024; Oliveira et al., 2019). Research findings always indicate the performance benefits are more correlated with depth of assimilation compared to presence of adoption, especially in SMEs where superficial adoption might not generate anything but a short-lived value (Badghish & Soomro, 2023; Rajaram et al., 2024). In addition to operational applications, recent reviews also note the application of AI in facilitating innovation of business models among SMEs in developing region (Chua, 2025).

According to the studies of South Asian (Lu et al., 2024) and Southeast Asian SMEs (Rahman, 2024; Chua, 2025), the use of AI is becoming more supportive of value creation and capture models, including digital bundling of services and data-driven pricing, though structural barriers to financial resiliency and competitiveness remain to be considered in terms of infrastructure, governance, and ethics (Rahman, 2024; Chua, 2025).

2.4 Financial Performance Outcomes

The most common dependent constructs are financial and operational results of the research on the adoption of artificial intelligence by SMEs reflecting the level of how AI

motivated initiatives can be converted into quantifiable business value (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Eze Ijeoma et al., 2025). Literature gives increasing reasons to propose that AI implementation is to be considered not solely through the prism of technological execution but rather through the prism of its role in the financial performance and efficiency of firms at the firm level (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Ines et al., 2024).

The experience of Southeast Asia suggests that SMEs that act in volatile and digitally evolving markets can gain disproportionate performance advantages with the use of AI when consistent with local market demands and organizational strengths (Sunandes et al., 2025; World Bank, 2020). Research indicates that SMEs that use AI to overcome labor constraints, enhance financial planning, and engage customers have better chances of accomplishing operational stability as well as financial sustainability (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Chua, 2025). Nevertheless, disparities in capability formation and unequal infrastructure have been generating unequal results throughout the region (OECD, 2024; Rahman, 2024).

Altogether, literature proves that the effect of AI adoption on financial performance of SMEs is contingent and not deterministic (Ayinaddis, 2025; Badghish & Soomro, 2024). The coexistence between AI adoption and the capabilities of firms, financial resources, and market condition is associated with positive results, but not technology adoption per se (Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024; Eze Ijeoma et al., 2025). Accordingly, the study proposes that GenAI adoption is positively associated with the financial performance of SMEs. However, this relationship is not automatic but conditioned upon the organizational contexts detailed across all prior themes discussed above namely, technological infrastructure, human factors, market pressures and financial capital.

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Generative AI adoption is positively associated with the financial

performance of SMEs. SMEs that have clear alignment between company specific goals and Generative AI capabilities are more likely to realize financial improvements upon adoption.

2.5 Talent, Skill Gaps and Human Capabilities in AI Adoption

Among the most crucial factors that can determine the success of artificial intelligence implementation in SMEs presented in literature is human capabilities (Benitez et al., 2024), especially with the most advanced systems like Generative AI (Ayinaddis, 2025; Badghish & Soomro, 2024). SMEs have a narrow range of managers and employees, which often complete several roles, which increases the value of personal skills, learning potential, and the role of managers in AI-linked projects (Kindström et al., 2022; Kraus et al., 2021).

Research indicates that SME owners and senior managers are the most important in AI adoption (Gupta, 2024), use case decisions and legitimization of AI aided decision making in the organization (Iyelolu et al., 2024). Most digital-savvy and open-minded managers will consider Generative AI as a decision-enhancing tool and not a threat to managerial control (Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024), which will further enable them to integrate it into their organizational practices (Ines et al., 2024).

Another mediating variable highlighted in the literature, which is the absorptive capacity (Bresciani et al., 2021), which refers to the capacity of the firm to identify, internalize, and utilize new knowledge, is crucial in the relationship between the adoption of AI and its performance outcome (Bresciani et al., 2021; Mariani & Dwivedi, 2024). The more learned cultures and experience with digital are the SMEs that can take AI insights into practice and implement them in strategies more easily, whereas companies with low

absorptive capacity struggle to go beyond surface-level adoption (Kraus et al., 2021; Badghish & Soomro, 2024).

The difference is especially pertinent to Generative AI which generates probabilistic and context dependent outputs that cannot be directly implemented but have to be interpreted by people (Dwivedi et al., 2023). The significance of human capabilities in determining the result of AI adoption is strengthened by regional studies found in Southeast Asia (Chua, 2025; Sunandes et al., 2025). Due to the specifics of the skills shortage, uneven education systems, and the inability to obtain AI-specific training quite often, SMEs in the region may experience compounded challenges that can hamper adoption and decrease the performance gains (Rahman, 2024; World Bank, 2020). Meanwhile, there is some evidence that the use of Generative AI in the compensation of labor shortages and increasing the flexibility of operations can be facilitated by the targeted upskilling and informal learning practices by the SMEs (OECD, 2024; Ayankoya et al., 2025).

Therefore, the study proposes that human capabilities positively influence GenAI adoption in SMEs, particularly through opportunity recognition, leadership framing, and learning readiness.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Human capabilities positively influence the relationship between Generative AI adoption and SME financial performance.

2.6 Technological Infrastructure and Data Readiness

In the literature, technological infrastructure and data preparedness are repeatedly cited as the main preconditions of successful adoption of artificial intelligence (Ayinaddis, 2025; Lu et al., 2022). In contrast to large businesses, SMEs have fragmented information systems, insufficient information standardization, and old technologies that restrict their

capacity to implement and scale sophisticated AI solutions (Kindström et al., 2022; OECD, 2021). Consequently, the technological preparedness is an important factor that defines whether the introduction of AI will result in significant performance gains instead of a one-off trial (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Benitez et al., 2024).

As demonstrated by the evidence of Southeast Asian SMEs (Chua, 2025), the issue of infrastructure inhibits access to data, yet it is also accompanied by the lack of bandwidth (Adepoju et al., 2024), unstable power (Rajaram et al., 2024), and poor institutional digital support of specific markets (Rahman, 2024). Comparative analysis conducted among the countries of the ASEAN (OECD, 2021) shows that these infrastructural vulnerabilities have a direct impact on the scalability and reliability of AI systems, which inhibits the mass to which the adoption of AI will result in long-term productivity and financial benefits (Rahman, 2024).

Conceptual and thematic review also suggests that, currently, high implementation costs and low levels of technological infrastructure are moderating factors that hinder the use of AI to enhance productivity among SMEs in Indonesia (Adepoju et al., 2024). Even when interests and capabilities are present, the SME's infrastructure also determines whether they can activate solutions such as GenAI into real tangible outcomes.

In general, the current studies imply that technological infrastructure and data readiness are critical factors that determine the presence or absence of significant financial and operational results of the Generative AI adoption (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Benitez et al., 2024). On the flip side, SME companies with lower IT infrastructure budget (Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024), has little control or abilities to facilitate its successful implementation of AI which in turn limits the potential of gaining effective operational and financial performance (Badghish & Soomro, 2024). Based on this, the study proposes that

technological capabilities positively influence GenAI adoption in SMEs by shaping implementation readiness and system fit.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Technological capabilities positively mediate the relationship between Generative AI adoption and SME financial performance.

2.7 Organizational Culture

It has become widely accepted that organizational culture and change management (Hughes et al, 2025) are the key conditions of the successful adoption of artificial intelligence in SMEs, especially in advanced systems like Generative AI, which do not only automatize the work but also change how decisions are made and practiced (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Raisch & Krakowski, 2021). Informal organization and centralized decision making involve the issue that SMEs can both expedite the adoption process by supporting leadership and impede it by resisting change based on the current cultural norms and managerial attitudes (Kindström et al., 2022; Kraus et al., 2021).

SMEs that frame Generative AI as a source of assistance to employees in the context of analysis, planning and problem solving (Gupta, 2024) are more likely to have higher rates of acceptance and involvement in comparison to those companies that promote the stories of cost-cutting or replacement of workers (OECD, 2024; Chua, 2025). This framing impacts the ways in which employees will work with AI and the incorporation of AI output into daily decision making (Ines et al., 2024; Mangifera et al., 2023). Southeast Asian regional research (Chua, 2025; Sunandes et al., 2025) also proves that organizational culture is an intermediary between AI implementation and performance outcomes (Chua, 2025; Sunandes et al., 2025).

In collectivist or hierarchical cultures, SMEs might be more deferential to leadership instructions, and this can be adopted easily but cannot be used to learn bottom

up or to gain feedback unless carefully handled (Rahman, 2024). This alignment is especially crucial to the applications of Generative AI that affect the planning process, forecasting processes, and the process of engaging the customer (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Eze Ijeoma et al., 2025) because these complex processes do not result in the outcomes as anticipated by the top organization leadership since the operations and execution team does not understand how to incorporate or in this case, use AI to augment the existing processes (Chua, 2025; Eze Ijeoma et al., 2025).

Therefore, it is hypothesized that leadership and culture, which are both related to human capabilities linked to organizational environmental factors, can act as an intervening factor. This intervening condition shapes whether GenAI is seen as a threat or an enabler which indicates that strong leadership alignment and company learning culture will support capability deployment and indirectly positively affect financial performance of companies when they adopt GenAI. Hence, Organizational Culture, is conceptualized as part of the broader Human Capabilities domain, particularly through leadership alignment, learning orientation, openness to experimentation, and knowledge-sharing culture. In addition, Proposition 1 is included to capture a more specific cultural mechanism: whether GenAI is framed as augmentation or replacement.

Proposition 1 (P1): SMEs that frame Generative AI adoption as an augmentation to existing human workflows and judgements rather than full automation are more likely to experience lesser resistance and smoother integration leading to stronger outcomes.

2.8 Financial Resource Constraints and ROI Considerations

A limitation of financial resources is well known in literature as one of the main factors (Rahman, 2024; Wonglimpiyarat, 2015) that influence the decision to adopt artificial intelligence in SMEs, especially in relation to high-tech technologies like

Generative AI that require both direct and indirect expenses (Wonglimpiyarat, 2015; World Bank, 2020). SMEs usually have limited access to capital resources, constrained cash flow status as well as greater vulnerability to investment risk, thus restricting their potential to make uncertain or long-term investments in technology (Gamage et al., 2020). The issue of return on investment is one of the key factors in determining AI adoption and assimilation within SMEs (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Eze Ijeoma et al., 2025).

The literature underscores that it is common in the context of SMEs to find it hard to measure the anticipated financial advantages of AI investments *ex ante*, especially when such advantages are dispersed, indirect, or manifested in several business functions (Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024; Mangifera et al., 2023). This ambiguity may result in the conservative behavior of investment wherein SMEs restrict the scope of AI to small scale pilots or the use of AI at low cost instead of taking on larger scale organizational integration (Ayinaddis, 2025; Badghish & Soomro, 2024).

Several studies draw a distinction between short term and long-term performance outcomes of AI adoption, citing that initial stages of implementation might be characterized by productivity effects, learning expenses, and short-term drops in productivity (Eze Ijeoma et al., 2025). Consequently, AI solutions focused on shorter-term operational savings might be chosen when SMEs do not need long-term strategic or analytical potential (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Gupta, 2024). According to recent sources, the financial limitations may be partially mitigated with the help of the public sector, grants, and subsidized digitalization programs that will stimulate the use of AI by SMEs (Asian Development Bank, 2022; OECD, 2024).

But according to the Southeast Asian experience, the knowledge and adoption of such programs are not even, and the administrative complexity may restrain their

effectiveness in smaller companies with inadequate management capacities (Rahman, 2024; Sunandes et al., 2025). Therefore, financial limitations still determine the magnitude and expanse of AI implementation in several SMEs (Chua, 2025; World Bank, 2020). Altogether, the current literature shows that financial resource limitation and ROI factor have a significant impact on the adoption and assimilation of Generative AI in SMEs (Ayinaddis, 2025; Eze Ijeoma et al., 2025).

The small financial ability, unpredictability in terms of returns, and lack of easy access to external financing may limit the level of adoption and delayed performance realized especially in resource-constrained settings (Wonglimpiyarat, 2015; World Bank, 2020). These results demonstrate the significance of financial limitations and technological, human, and cultural aspects investigation to realize the circumstances in which the adoption of AI can lead to sustainable financial performance that is further discussed in the following paragraphs of this chapter. From this, the study proposes that financial resources positively influence GenAI adoption in SMEs. This means that firms with stronger financial backing are better positioned to move identified use cases into implementation.

Hypothesis 4 (H4): Financial resources positively influence the relationship between Generative AI adoption and SME financial performance.

Proposition 2 (P2): When Generative AI is perceived to be too costly or lacking near-term ROI, regardless of strategic interest, GenAI adoption and impact tends to be delayed or less effective.

2.9 Market Pressure and Customer Demand

The pressure of the market and the demand of the customers are deemed as highly significant external forces that influence, on the one hand, the decision to adopt the

artificial intelligence in the SMEs and, on the other hand, the company operations in the highly competitive and digitally-intensive market (Barkley & Jokonya, 2024; Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990). In contrast to large business ventures that can implement AI proactively as a strategy in long term strategic positioning, SMEs usually implement AI reactively as a response to competitive pressures, customer demands, and industry requirements (Ayinaddis, 2025; Badghish & Soomro, 2024).

The customer demand has become a notably relevant reason behind the introduction of AI in SMEs (McKinsey Global Institute, 2023; OECD, 2023). Empirical studies show that customers are becoming increasingly demanding when it comes to faster responses (Livingston, 2024), customized experiences, recommendations based on data, and uniformity of the quality of services provided through the digital channels (Dwivedi et al., 2023). A few articles note that Generative AI is especially adept to handling customer driven pressures because of its capacity to generate customized outputs on a high scale, such as marketing pieces, customer communications, and decision support insights (Dwivedi et al., 2023; McKinsey Global Institute, 2023).

In the case of SMEs, such capabilities would provide the potential to estimate the service sophistication of larger companies without corresponding growth in labor expenses, which would improve the equality on a competitive level (Ayankoya et al., 2025; OECD, 2024). The literature, however, also warns that customers facing AI applications increase reputational risks in case the output is inaccurate, inconsistent, or incompatible with the brand values (Deloitte, 2024; OECD, 2023). There are also industry-specific processes that contribute to the effects of market pressure on the adoption of AI (Arranz et al., 2023; Kindström et al., 2022).

In the retail, logistics, financial services, and professional services industry, SMEs

are more exposed to the pressure to go digital because of platform competition and technology enabled entrants (Eze Ijeoma et al., 2025; Mangifera et al., 2023). Conversely, SMEs that cater to traditional or relationship-based industries might have less short-term pressure but have more long-term exposure to competitive displacement in case of failure to adopt (Ayinaddis, 2025; Gamage et al., 2020). There is some evidence in Southeast Asia indicating that SMEs in digitally progressive markets feel increased pressure on the need to implement AI enabled practices on behalf of customers, partners, and regulators, despite not having internal capabilities to do so (Chua, 2025; Sunandes et al., 2025).

Therefore, this study proposes that market factors positively influence GenAI adoption in SMEs by creating urgency through competitive pressure and customer expectations.

Hypothesis 5 (H5): Market factors positively influence the relationship between Generative AI adoption and SME financial performance. SMEs facing more intense market pressures and customer expectations are more likely to prioritize Generative AI adoption in processes.

2.10 Literature Gaps and Research Questions

Overall, the extensive and multidisciplinary literature reviewed in this study suggests that Generative AI can improve SME performance under certain conditions, particularly through operational enhancement, decision support, and improved responsiveness (Gupta, 2024). This shows there is growing evidence that GenAI can improve SME performance under certain conditions. However, there is still limited research that investigates the mechanisms through which GenAI adoption leads to financial value in SMEs, especially in Southeast Asia (Rahman, 2024; Chua, 2025). In other words, the broader literature increasingly suggests that GenAI works, but the

process through which it creates value is still largely insufficiently explained, especially in Southeast Asian SME context.

The review absorbed the perspectives of information systems, entrepreneurship, strategic management, and SME finance in order to compose a holistic view of how the process of AI adoption takes place in the constraint of a resource-based organization setting (Ayinaddis, 2025; Dwivedi et al., 2023). Taken altogether, the literature has proven that, despite the trend of growing AI adoption among SMEs, its performance results are uneven and greatly dependent on both the internal capabilities and external conditions (Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024; Badghish & Soomro, 2024). More specifically, the Southeast Asian literature has not gone far enough in explaining how SME leaders navigate these constraints in practice, despite early evidence that GenAI related gains are possible (Rahman, 2024).

In particular, previous studies have tended to focus on large enterprises in developed markets (Mangifera et al., 2023), who have more abundant resources and better infrastructure (Mariani & Dwivedi, 2024). It creates gaps in understanding whether the same performance benefits apply to small and medium-sized enterprises operating in the complex and often resource-constrained environments of Southeast Asia (Rahman, 2024; Rajaram et al., 2024). This is the core point of differentiation of this study: it does not simply examine whether GenAI adoption is beneficial in general, but investigates how value is realized among Southeast Asian SMEs operating with narrower resource bases, uneven infrastructure, and more immediate financial constraints.

In the studies reviewed, GenAI is being conceptualized increasingly as a decision augmentation technology (Ines et al., 2024), rather than just a tool of operational automation, especially in the context of SMEs where managerial judgement is a key factor

in the performance of firms (Raisch and Krakowski, 2021). New evidence is that Generative AI can be used to improve the quality, efficiency and flexibility of decisions (Ayankoya et al., 2025), yet only with proper human capabilities, technology infrastructure, and organizational preparedness (Ayankoya et al., 2025; OECD, 2024).

This supports the argument that the implementation of AI is not enough to ensure a positive change in performance, which proves the need to analyze the contextual and situational variables (Kraus et al., 2021). Human capabilities, such as AI literacy, managerial preparedness, and absorptive capacity, are consistently cited in the literature as essential facilitating factors of effective AI assimilation in SMEs (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Gupta, 2024). Nevertheless, many SMEs still experience a high level of skills gaps and the lack of access to training, which limits their potential to use the results of AI in making practical business decisions (Iyelolu et al., 2024; OECD, 2024). Although the existing literature recognizes the significance of human factors, there are very few studies that empirically investigate these factors shape the relationship between AI adoption and financial performance outcomes (Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024; Ayinaddis, 2025).

Technological infrastructure, such as data preparedness, system integration, and digital infrastructure, are also highlighted as the essential prerequisites of AI adoption (Arranz et al., 2023; Lu et al., 2022). However, existing research stops at technology adoption or implementation (Hughes et al., 2025), without examining how adoption translates into measurable financial or operational results (Gupta, 2024). There is also a lack of mixed-methods studies that connect quantitative patterns of adoption with qualitative insights about how these technologies are experienced by SME leaders (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Gupta, 2024; Iyelolu et al., 2024;). Regardless, the body of literature analyzing technological readiness and performance outcomes together in a single

analytical framework is also limited (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Eze Ijeoma et al., 2025).

The issue of financial resources limitations and ROI arise as the continuing impediments to the utilization of AI in SMEs (Wonglimpiyarat, 2015; World Bank, 2020). Although some of the studies emphasize the cost sensitivity of SMEs and uncertainty of returns to AI investment, not many of them empirically determine how financial constraints combine with other organizational capabilities to create strong adoption and performance outcomes (Abdul Wahab & Radmehr, 2024; Ayankoya et al., 2025). This disparity restricts the comprehension of why certain SMEs gain considerable advantages as a result of AI adoption compared to others that gain few or no results (Ayinaddis, 2025; Drydakis, 2022). It is generally accepted that market pressure and customer demand are the most important external factors that spur the use of AI in SMEs (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Barkley & Jokonya, 2024).

Nevertheless, most current research works assume environmental variables to be background conditions (Arranz et al., 2023; Barkley et al., 2024; Benitez et al., 2024), but does not clearly explain how they interact with other organizational conditions in shaping adoption and value realization (OECD, 2021; Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990). Consequently, little work has been conducted on the interaction between market forces and firm specific capabilities, especially in dynamic and developing market environments like Southeast Asia (Sunandes et al., 2025; World Bank, 2020). In terms of performance outcomes, the literature evidence is inconclusive about the financial and operational effects of AI implementation in SMEs (Eze Ijeoma et al., 2025; Mangifera et al., 2023). Although gains in efficiency and speed of decision-making are relatively common, financial benefits are either delayed, uneven, or require other complementary abilities (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Ines et al., 2024). In this inconsistency, the necessity to use empirical models that specifically address

moderating conditions and intermediate mechanisms mediating between AI adoption and performance outcomes is highlighted (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Teece, 2018).

To address the gaps identified, this study adopts a mixed-methods design that integrates PLS-SEM with qualitative thematic analysis to explore the relationship between GenAI adoption and performance (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Gupta, 2024; Iyelolu et al., 2024). This allows the research to move beyond a single method approach to a mixed methods approach to examine the factors that affect financial performance with GenAI adoption.

The study investigates the four contextual factors, namely, human capabilities (Benitez et al., 2024), technological infrastructure (Barkley et al., 2024), financial resources (Arranz et al., 2023), and market pressures (Bresciani et al., 2021) and their influence on financial performance with the adoption of GenAI. These dimensions are drawn from the TOE framework and are commonly cited in digital transformation literature as critical to successful technology outcomes (Hughes et al. 2025; Mariani & Dwivedi, 2024; Paetz, 2023).

Building on these insights, this section concludes by restating the three research questions that guide this study:

- RQ1: How do human capabilities, technological capabilities, financial resources, and market dynamics shape the relationship between Generative AI adoption and SME financial performance?
- RQ2: What themes emerge from SME leaders' experiences that explain the pathways, barriers, and enabling conditions for translating Generative AI adoption into financial
- RQ3: What is the relationship between Generative AI adoption and financial

performance among SMEs in Southeast Asia?

2.11 Hypotheses and Propositions Development

Building upon the literature gaps identified and the research questions posed above, the hypotheses and propositions are developed based on existing literature and grounded in TOE framework. It focuses on reflecting both the direct effects of Generative AI adoption and the roles of organizational and environment factors.

The research takes a technological determinist (Block et al., 2021) view in assuming the adoption of GenAI is a value-generating organizational capability, which can be used by SMEs to improve financial performance (Rajaram et al., 2024).

Hypotheses

H1: Generative AI adoption is positively associated with the financial performance of SMEs.

H2: Human capabilities positively influence the relationship between Generative AI adoption and SME financial performance.

H3: Technological capabilities positively influence the relationship between Generative AI adoption and SME financial performance.

H4: Financial resources positively influence the relationship between Generative AI adoption and SME financial performance.

H5: Market factors positively influence the relationship between Generative AI adoption and SME financial performance.

Propositions

P1: SMEs that frame Generative AI adoption as an augmentation to existing human workflows and judgements rather than full automation are more likely to experience lesser

resistance and smoother integration leading to stronger outcomes.

P2: When Generative AI is perceived to be too costly or lacking near-term ROI, regardless of strategic interest, GenAI adoption and impact tends to be delayed or less effective.

2.12 Chapter Summary

This chapter pulled together key insights from the literature to explore how GenAI is being adopted by SME companies, especially highlighting Southeast Asia contexts. Using the Technology–Organization–Environment (TOE) framework as a guide, the areas namely, human capabilities, technology infrastructure, financial resources, and market pressures are explored. These are the main conditions that shape how well SMEs can actually turn GenAI tools into real business value.

While there is a growing body of research on GenAI adoption in general, most of them look at these factors separately, without exploring much of how they might work together. Also, a lot of them still come from studies on large firms in more developed economies, which makes it harder to apply directly to the SMEs in the environment of Southeast Asia. This review therefore argues that GenAI adoption is not simply the uptake of a new digital tool, but a context-dependent process shaped by human capabilities, technological readiness, funding conditions, and market pressures. Taken together, these conditions form the basis for examining not only whether SMEs adopt GenAI, but how adoption is more likely to translate into meaningful business value.

The next chapter outlines the research design, methodology, and analytical procedures used to examine these relationships. Through a mixed-methods approach combining both quantitative and qualitative research, the study aims to generate practical

and theoretical insights to which SMEs derive value in form of financial impact from GenAI adoption.

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter explains how this research study was designed and conducted. It outlines the study's mixed methods approach which combines data from quantitative modelling to qualitative interviews to provide a good understanding of contextual factors that GenAI adoption and its corresponding financial outcome. The rationale for this methodology is also explained.

For both the quantitative and qualitative approach, it describes the research process from sampling, instrument design, data collection, to PLS-SEM and thematic coding analysis. Each decision is tied to the practical context of SMEs in Southeast Asia.

3.1 Introduction

This chapter provides the research methodology that is used to investigate how the adoption of Generative AI can be associated with the financial and operational success of small and medium sized enterprises in Southeast Asia. Based directly on the theoretical framework presented in Chapter 2, the methodology aims to empirically test the association between Generative AI adoption and SME financial performance while examining how human capabilities, technological capabilities, financial resources, and market factors shape the conditions under which adoption occurs.

This research assumes mixed methods research design given the complexity and contextual nature behind the adoption of Generative AI in SMEs. The quantitative component facilitates hypothesis testing, and generalizing to the target SMEs population, whereas the qualitative component allows in-depth examination of the organizational processes, decision-making, and situational factors that cannot be adequately described by

a survey. Based on the hypotheses (see chapters 1 and 2), this chapter presents the methodological approach applied to empirically test the proposed relationships quantitatively and explore the recurring themes from qualitative results to explain why these relationships reveal the phenomena the way they do.

In practical terms, the quantitative phase tests whether GenAI adoption is associated with SME financial performance (H1) and whether human capabilities, technological capabilities, financial resources, and market factors influence GenAI adoption (H2–H5). The qualitative phase then explains how these conditions operate in practice and why their roles may differ across the adoption journey.

3.2 Research Philosophy and Approach

The study is underpinned by a pragmatic research philosophy, according to which there is no single methodological tradition that can be used to explain complex organizational phenomena (Barkley & Jokonya, 2024; Wynn & Williams, 2012), including the adoption of AI and performance outcomes. Pragmatism carries the underlying belief in adopting various approaches to answering research questions, facilitating explanatory and practical relevance, rather than following a particular epistemological position (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

This aligns with the research's key goal to uncover significant statistical relationships among the 4 contextual factors through structured quantitative phase while also capturing nuanced, experiential insights through our qualitative explanatory inquiry. Such pragmatic approaches have been used in similar studies by Rajaram et al. (2024) and Benitez et al. (2024) where they sought to find the intersection between technical systems and human or environmental variables when investigating digital transformation outcomes.

Regarding epistemology, the quantitative stage assumes a post positivist viewpoint (Creswell & Poth, 2018), as it aims to determine patterns, relationships, and statistically significant effects among variables by testing the hypothesis. The qualitative stage is interpreted in terms of an interpretivist approach where the researcher will be able to investigate managerial perceptions, experiences, and dynamic situational contexts of Generative AI adoption in SMEs (Barkley & Jokonya, 2024).

This mixed approach and alignment provides flexibility across the data types (Hughes et al., 2025) and exemplifies the strength of triangulating both empirical measurement and context-based understanding (Chua, 2025). Hence, this synthesis allows the triangulation of results and strengthens the validity and the strength of the research results (Chua, 2025).

3.2.1 Philosophy Justification and Reference to Prior Studies

The literature review revealed that many studies adopt a single-method design, which often leads to partial or incomplete insights which further justify the pragmatic, mixed-methods approach used in this study. For example, Badghish and Soomro (2024) and Gupta (2024) used TOE-based quantitative surveys to identify adoption drivers. While their findings offer clear statistical structure, they do not capture deeper organizational dynamics like managerial interpretation. They explain what factors matter but do not explain how or why it works that way.

Ayinaddis (2025), on the other hand, critiqued the TOE model for oversimplifying the complex interdependencies between technology, organization, and environment which results in viewing these interrelated dimensions in isolation. Moreover, the model tends to underrepresent broader cultural (Rahman, 2024) and socioeconomic influences (Rajaram et al., 2024) that are especially relevant in emerging economies.

Furthermore, Gupta (2024) noted that models like Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) which are foundational in most technology adoption studies, often struggle to account for the evolving nature of nascent technologies such as GenAI. Predefined survey instruments are too rigid to capture the changing and unpredictable ways SMEs experiment with AI tools (Chua, 2025; Gupta, 2024).

The gaps identified across past studies reinforce the need for a research design that is both pragmatic and rich in context (Hughes et al., 2025). This not only enhances the explanatory power but also improves the practical relevance of the findings which is especially relevant in evolving nature of GenAI (Gupta, 2024) and socioeconomic context of Southeast Asia (Chua, 2025).

3.3 Research Design

This study uses sequential explanatory mixed methods design (Dawadi et al., 2021). This study is carried out in two stages. The initial stage of the research will be a quantitative survey of SME leaders and decision makers in order to test the relationships that are hypothesized in the conceptual framework.

The second stage involves a semi-structured interview of a sample of survey participants to elucidate contextually and give more insight on the quantitative findings. The design is specifically adapted to the study of new technologies like Generative AI, where statistical relationships can be better understood qualitatively to offer explanation of the causality, boundary conditions, and challenges to implement it (Dwivedi et al., 2023). The qualitative results are applied not to simply supplement the quantitative results. Rather, it is used to explain the unexpected and refine the non-obvious quantitative patterns. Such insights will be built not from a single interview insight but from repeated cases across multiple cases where factor sequencing logic provides stable and credible explanation for

the quantitative results.

3.4 Conceptual Framework and Hypothesized Relationships

Figure 2 presents the conceptual diagram guiding this study. At the center of this model, GenAI adoption serves as the key adoption construct linking contextual conditions to SME financial performance. The financial performance of SMEs is the dependent variable, and the four factors are: human capabilities, technological capabilities, funding capital and market factors. The control variables are firm size, industry type, geographic region, and time frame of the adoption of AI.

Figure 2

Conceptual Framework Flow

This is posed formally in the following equation format:

$$GA = \beta_0 + \beta_1(HC) + \beta_2(TC) + \beta_3(FC) + \beta_4(MF) + \epsilon_1; FP = \beta_0 + \beta_1(GA) + \epsilon_2$$

Where:

- GA = Generative AI Adoption (mediator)
- FP = Financial Performance (dependent variable)
- HC, TC, FC, MF = Human, Technological, Financial, and Market Factors
- ϵ = Error term

3.4.1 Hypotheses Testing Approach

The research follows a mixed-methods approach, the quantitative component of which will be the partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) to test the five hypotheses (H1-H5) posed in the study. The conceptual model is organized to capture the conceptual knowledge that human capabilities, technological capabilities, funding capital and market factors all serve as antecedents to the adoption of Generative AI. Later, the level of adoption is an indicator of financial performance of SMEs.

Hypothesis H1 tests the direct effects of GenAI adoption on financial performance. Hypotheses H2 through H5 examine if and how these contextual variables influence GenAI adoption in SMEs.

This method of analysis is aligned with the Technology Organization Environment (TOE) framework and assumes the level of success with GenAI varies with social- and human capital endowment (e.g., the level of human, or technological preparedness). In this dissertation, these factors are operationalized empirically as antecedent contextual factors influencing GenAI adoption, which is then associated with financial performance.

PLS-SEM is particularly appropriate for this research because it is predictive by nature and supports the estimation of complex models with multiple latent constructs in exploratory settings where theory is still developing.

This approach is chosen due to the requirement to preserve both parsimony and statistical power in the structural model and is comparable to other TOE-based research designs (Ayinaddis, 2025; Badghish and Soomro, 2024). This approach has implications as mentioned in Chapters 4 and 5.

3.5 Population and Sampling

This section outlines the methodological approach to define the research's target population and the strategy adopted to select a representative sample. The credibility and generalizability of this research depend on the careful delineation of the population from which participants are selected here. This is in alignment with the research focus on the real-world application of Generative AI in Southeast Asia where the selected population is focused on SMEs with a minimum size and staff count that have adopted GenAI solutions.

3.5.1 Target Population

The target group includes small and medium sized enterprises that have embraced, are embracing, or even are experimenting with Generative AI tools. The definition of SMEs is tied to generally recognized criteria (as defined earlier), such as the number of employees and revenue levels, which are in line with those of the OECD and the World Bank (OECD, 2021; World Bank, 2020).

The respondents are owners, founders, senior managers or functional leaders who are directly involved in AI based decision making, such as finance decision making, operations decision making, strategy decision making or digital transformation decision making.

3.5.2 Sampling Strategy

The sample of SMEs that have been exposed to the adoption of Generative AI is identified through a purposive sampling strategy (Soni, 2024). It is understood that while purposive sampling ensures the relevance of the selected SMEs with exposure to GenAI, it limits statistical generalizability beyond the sampled population (Soni, 2024). Hence, the findings are consequently generalizable within the context of the type of selected Southeast Asian SMEs who has exposure to GenAI than all Southeast Asian SMEs.

In the case of the quantitative component of the methodology, the minimum sample size is established by statistical power analysis, in order to be sufficiently large to support partial least squares structural equation modeling. The qualitative stage will use maximum variation sampling to help in the collection of various views among industries, firms, and levels of adoption maturity.

Quantitative

To establish statistical validity for Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), power analysis was conducted using G*Power 3.1. With an estimated effect size of 0.30, $\alpha = 0.05$, and power = 0.80, the analysis determined that a minimum of 100 observations is required to detect significant relationships across four latent constructs and two control variables. To accommodate potential dropouts or unusable responses, a target sample size of over 200 SMEs was established. Recruitment is executed through researcher's professional networks, professional SME bodies and professional SME panel, allowing access to verified business respondents across Southeast Asia. Survey distribution is targeted at business owners and key decision-makers, applying the following inclusion criteria for the SMEs:

- Annual turnover \geq SGD 250,000.
- Minimum of 10 employees.
- Registered and currently operating in one of the Southeast Asian countries.

Qualitative

Maximum variation sampling strategy is used to select participants from the quantitative pool who represent a diversity of industries, adoption levels, and geographies. This approach ensures a breadth of perspectives and deepens understanding of the contextual and managerial factors behind adoption decisions (Chua, 2025).

Sampling is also performed in batches until data saturation is reached: when additional interviews no longer reveal new themes (Hughes et al., 2025). The expected number of interviews is between 30 and 40, based on prior studies of emerging technology adoption in SMEs (Chua, 2025; Denny & Weckesser, 2022).

3.6 Data Collection

Following the definition of the sample, this section details the systematic procedures for collecting empirical data. As this research is using sequential explanatory mixed-methods design, it is broken down into two distinct phases. The initial phase involves a quantitative survey designed to test hypothesized relationships. The subsequent phase uses semi-structured interviews to explore contextual nuances and themes to explain the statistical findings. This dual approach ensures the breadth of generalizable trends as well as rich contextual insights. The following subsections will describe the development of the data collection instruments.

3.6.1 Quantitative Data Collection

Quantitative data is gathered using a structured online questionnaire. The survey contained tested and modified measurement questions based on previous AI implementation and SME performance reports (Badghish and Soomro, 2024; Gupta, 2024; Soni, 2024). Multi-item Likert scales (e.g., 1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree) are used to determine constructs so that the captured data can be used to understand a range of perceptions and attitudes (Hair et al., 2022). In this case, we utilize it to understand the use of generative AI: which is assessed using metrics that reflect the intensity of use and functional usage that include content creation, customer engagement, product development, and strategy decision making (Rajaram et al. 2024).

To ensure the validity and trustworthiness of the research's survey data, each

construct is operationalized based on existing literature (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Gupta, 2024; Soni, 2024) and market environments (Mangifera et al., 2023). The following breakdown explains how each construct is measured and their alignment in theory.

1. **Generative AI Adoption (Independent Variable - H1):** This construct captures essence of GenAI deployment in SMEs, operationalized through multiple items that examine and reflect both process-level and firm-wide adoption considerations (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Gupta, 2024).
 - a) the range of business functions using GenAI (e.g., customer service, marketing, internal automation) (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Gupta, 2024),
 - b) the intensity of use across departments (Lu et al., 2022), and
 - c) the strategic versus operational intent behind adoption (Iyelolu et al., 2024).
2. **Financial Performance (Dependent Variable - H1):** Financial performance is measured through self-reported perceptual items on a five-point Likert scale, capturing changes in profitability, revenue growth, cost efficiency, and market share since adopting GenAI. Prior literature has validated the use of perceptual financial performance in SME contexts where audited financials are often unavailable in such market segments (Ayankoya et al., 2025; Mangifera et al., 2023).
3. **Human Capabilities (Moderating Variable - H2):** This construct evaluates the readiness and capacity of human resources to support GenAI.

- a) digital literacy of staff (Benitez et al., 2024; Hughes et al., 2025);
- b) managerial understanding of AI technologies (Benitez et al., 2024; Hughes et al. 2025); and
- c) organizational learning culture (Benitez et al., 2024).

4. **Technological Capabilities (Moderating Variable - H3):** Technological readiness is assessed through items related to the existence of digital infrastructure (e.g., cloud platforms, CRM/ERP systems) and system interoperability where the constructs are drawn from Barkley et al. (2024), Shahadat et al. (2023), and Avinaddis (2024).
5. **Financial Resources (Moderating Variable - H4):** This construct measures perceived financial ability and desire to invest in AI initiatives. It includes items relating to available discretionary budgets (Barkley et al., 2024) as well as perceived ROI risk tolerance (Chakraborty et al., 2025; Mangifera et al, 2023).
6. **Market Factors (Moderating Variable - H5):** This reflects external pressures including competitive intensity and customer demand for GenAI powered services. The questions include how competitor behavior, client expectations (Flaminiano, 2025), and industry norms are influencing GenAI adoption decisions (Bresciani et al., 2021).

3.6.2 Qualitative Data Collection

The qualitative data was collected via semi-structured interviews of the selected respondents of the surveys. The conceptual framework and the quantitative results are applied to develop an interview protocol. Interviews were based on the desire to identify the reasons behind the adoption of AI, how it was adopted, organizational issues, perceived

performance implications, and situational factors. The interviews are carried out in either physical or virtual- recorded interviews with consent and transcribed verbatim to be analyzed.

The design of the interview questions was informed directly by both the conceptual framework (see Figure 2) and key constructs derived from the literature review. Each question was aligned with one of the major themes: human capabilities, technological infrastructure, financial constraints, organizational culture, and market pressures. This alignment ensured that the qualitative stage provided explanatory depth and contextual richness to support and elaborate the quantitative findings (Barkley & Jokonya, 2024; Creswell & Poth, 2018).

1. Adoption Motivation and Decision-Making

- a. **Sample Question:** “When did your firm first start looking at GenAI and what motivated that interest?”
- b. This is drawn from literature which indicates top-down decision-making in SME contexts by Gupta (2024) and Kraus et al. (2021). It is also aligned with RQ3 and H1 where it is designed to understand the nuances of implementation than just adoption status (Dwivedi et al., 2023; Gupta, 2024).

2. Human and Organizational Capabilities

- a. **Sample Questions:** “*How would you describe your team’s readiness to work with AI tools?*”; “*What cultural or change-management factors helped or hindered adoption?*”

- b. This is linked to the importance of organizational digital readiness (Benitez et al., 2024; Bresciani et al., 2021) and any skills gaps and organizational culture barriers (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Iyelolu et al., 2024). These questions seek to uncover findings to build upon quantitative findings for H2.

3. Technological Readiness and Challenges

- a. **Sample Question:** “Were there any legacy or integration hurdles? How did you overcome them?”; “What existing digital systems did GenAI have to plug into, and how smooth was that?”
- b. These questions address the technological context (H3) and are crucial for understanding the prerequisites for successful adoption. It will also help uncover insights into data infrastructure challenges cited across Southeast Asian SMEs (Adepoju et al., 2025; Chua, 2025).

4. Market and Environmental Factors

- a. **Sample Question:** “When did your firm first start looking at GenAI and what motivated that interest?”
- b. These questions explore the external environmental pressures (H5) that drive adoption, such as reactive adoption due to competitive pressures (Ayinaddis, 2025; Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990). The questions are also directed and aim to uncover the qualitative evidence of market and competitive pressures cited in the literature (Barkley & Jokonya, 2024; Bresciani et al., 2021).

5. Funding Capital

- a. **Sample Question:** “How was the investment in Generative AI funded?”; “What were the key considerations when evaluating the cost versus the expected return on investment (ROI)?”
- b. These questions dive directly into the financial realities of SMEs in Southeast Asia which is linked to H4. Given resource constraints as a defining factor affecting SMEs (Ayankoya et al. 2025; Wonglimpiyarat, 2015) this will provide further understanding upon quantitative data.

6. Performance Outcomes and Reflections

Sample Question: “In your view, how has GenAI affected revenue, costs, or profitability so far?”; “What were the biggest enablers and obstacles, and why?”; “Is there anything else you wish policy-makers understood about SMEs and AI to establish policies and grants on?”

- a. Addressing the core of RQ3, these questions seek to connect AI adoption to performance outcomes from the perspective of the decision-maker. Apart from obtaining direct data on financial performance outcomes, this is also the final chance to explore and illicit any expanding themes that goes along with GenAI adoption from interviewee (Badghish & Soomro, 2024).

Each question block was flexibly structured to allow for participant-led narratives while ensuring consistency across interviews. The semi-structured format enabled emergent insights while still maintaining alignment with the conceptual framework and quantitative constructs. This methodological triangulation helps validate the mixed-methods design and enhances trustworthiness (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018).

3.7 Data Analysis

This chapter outlines the analytical framework used to synthesize the data collected in the previous phase. To stay true to the study's mixed-methods design, the analyses follow a dual yet integrated path. For the quantitative data, Partial Least Squares modeling (PLS-SEM) is performed to test the structural relationships proposed in the conceptual framework. For the qualitative data, a systematic process of thematic and axial coding is used to identify and obtain themes emerging from the interviews. Ultimately, the objective is to integrate the findings from these two analyses to allow rich qualitative insights to provide contextual explanations for the statistical results generated by the quantitative model.

3.7.1 Quantitative Analysis

Quantitative data was parsed through two key processes. First, descriptive analysis of all non-Likert scales were performed. Data analysis was computed for all demographic and categorical variables to check for anomalies and distribution properties. Second, Likert-scaled construct data were cleaned for PLS-SEM analysis. They are coded and assessed for suitability for PLS-SEM processing.

Hypothesis H1 is tested by measuring the direct relationship between the adoption of Generative AI and the financial performance of SMEs. Hypotheses H2 through H5 are tested by examining the direct relationships between human capabilities, technological capabilities, financial resources and market factors with respect to GenAI adoption. Bootstrapping with 5,000 subsamples is used to derive robust standard errors and p-values (Hair et al., 2022; Mangifera et al., 2023). Cohen's f^2 is calculated to assess local effect sizes. R^2 and Q^2 values are used to examine the predictive relevance and explained variance of the structural model (Hair et al. 2022).

The PLS-SEM follows a two-step methodology. The measurement model is first evaluated in terms of reliability and validity based on the composite reliability, average variance extracted and discriminant validity. Internal consistency is checked using Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability (CR) with acceptable thresholds of 0.70 for both indicators (Hair et al., 2022). Convergent validity is assessed through Average Variance Extracted (AVE), with a threshold of ≥ 0.50 (Hair et al., 2022). Discriminant validity is evaluated using the Fornell-Larcker criterion and Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio to ensure construct independence (Hair et al., 2022). Multicollinearity is also checked using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), with acceptable values below 5.0 (Hair et al., 2022). Second, the structural model is tested to examine assumed relationships and moderation effects. Significance of path coefficients and explanatory power (R^2) are used to assess model adequacy (Hair et al. 2022; Benitez et al., 2024). Based on p-values derived from 5,000 resamples, path coefficients are considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ with t-values exceeding 1.96 at 5% level and 2.58 at 1% level (Hair et al., 2022). Explanatory power is evaluated using R^2 values, where 0.25, 0.5 and 0.75 reflects weak, moderate and strong levels of explanatory power (Hair et al., 2022).

3.7.2 Qualitative Analysis

The qualitative component was to supplement and clarify the quantitative results by learning how, under what circumstances, and why Generative AI adoption can affect financial and operational outcomes in SMEs. Following the sequential explanatory mixed methods design, qualitative analysis was carried out following the initial quantitative analysis and the express aim of interpreting the observed statistical relations and clarifying the comprehension of the key contextual constructs outlined in the conceptual model.

The qualitative analysis was based on a multi-stage, systematic coding method based on open coding, axial coding, and selective integration (Chua, 2025). This approach made it possible to systematically abstract raw data of interviews to theoretically relevant patterns aligned with the hypotheses of the study. The three stages of analysis were completed sequentially. Thematic codes obtained out of the open-ended queries in the quantitative data collections are then prequalified. Second, a pilot sample of 20 interviews was examined to determine preliminary themes, and directional consistency with constructs that are formed in quantitative research.

Third, an additional thirteen interviews were carried out and examined in order to check the convergence, as well as check for any new themes that were discovered until thematic saturation is established. This approach adds the thickness of evidence to the categories that are in place especially as applied to market dynamics, capability constraints, and performance mechanisms.

Axial coding was thereafter utilized to determine associations between open codes, and to group them into higher-level thematic groups. The step concentrated on grouping similar codes based on causal conditions, contextual factors, intervening factors, and performance outcomes, thus allowing the establishment of organized directions between AI adoption and performance-related outcomes.

3.8 Reliability, Validity and Ethical Considerations

Quantitative reliability and validity are promoted by means of making use of the existing measurement scales, pilot testing the survey instrument, and the statistical evaluation of construct reliability and validity. The procedural remedies that handle common method bias include questionnaire design and statistical tests. As such, items are drawn from recognized frameworks in technology adoption and SME performance

research such as Soni (2024), Gupta (2024) and Badghish & Soomro (2024). To assess construct reliability, Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability (CR) are also computed to ensure internal consistency (Hair et al., 2022). Convergent validity will be evaluated using Average Variance Extracted (AVE), with a threshold of ≥ 0.50 indicating sufficient shared variance among indicators (Hair et al., 2022). Discriminant validity will be assessed using the Fornell-Larcker criterion and cross-loadings, consistent with recommended practices in PLS-SEM modeling (Benitez et al., 2024).

Credibility, transferability, dependability and confirmability guarantee qualitative trustworthiness. Credibility, through triangulation of sources during interview transcription and interpretation stages, is enhanced. Transferability is also supported by providing rich descriptions of SME nuanced contexts. Dependability is maintained through an audit trail that documents methodological decisions, while confirmability is assured through reflective journaling and peer debriefing (Ayinaddis, 2025)

This study obtained ethical approval before data was collected. All the respondents provided informed and voluntary consent. Participants were informed about the purpose and procedures of research, and provided explicit, voluntary consent. Confidentiality was ensured by the anonymization of the data and its safe storage. The participants are advised that they have the right to withdraw and they will not be penalized (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

3.9 Chapter Summary

The chapter outlined the methodology used to research on how GenAI adoption mediates the financial performance of SMEs in Southeast Asia through examining the factors. The research philosophy employed is pragmatic and is designed as a sequential explanatory mixed-method approach. It combines quantitative statistical modeling with contextual qualitative inquiry to better understand both measurable patterns and provide

rich contextual insights.

The mixed-methods approach is in response to identified limitations in prior literature which often relied on single method approach (Barkley & Jokonya, 2024; Wynn & Williams, 2012) which is not holistic enough to capture certain organizational complexity (Ayinaddis, 2025). It is also grounded in the TOE framework and conceptualizes GenAI adoption as the key adoption construct linking four contextual factors: human capabilities, technological capabilities, funding capital, and market factors, to Southeast Asian SME's financial performance.

A conceptual framework is introduced and structured into equation modelling with hypotheses H1 to H5 tested using PLS-SEM. Technical details were discussed including the quantitative sampling strategy to ensure the statistical power and data is representative of its operationalized constructs.

Qualitative data analysis in this research adopts grounded theory coding method (Strauss & Corbin, 1998) which begins from open coding to axial coding to generate nuanced categories and themes. The iterative and integrated nature of this design allowed for theoretical triangulation (Hair et al., 2022) to enhance the credibility and validity of the findings.

Overall, this chapter provides the empirical foundation for the analysis that is presented in the later chapters. Next, Chapter 4 will present the quantitative and qualitative results of the hypothesis testing, revealing patterns and interactions between GenAI adoption and SME performance.

Chapter 4

Results

In this chapter, the key results of the quantitative survey as well as the qualitative interviews are presented. Combined, these findings give an all-inclusive perspective on how SMEs in Southeast Asia are embracing Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) and what effects it has on their financial and operation performances. The chapter is separated into two sections.

Section 4.1 Quantitative Results presents the findings of the quantitative analysis, completed on survey data of 232 SMEs in the region. These findings challenge the five research hypotheses presented above, investigating the impacts of human capabilities, technological preparedness, investment capital, and market pressures in the adoption of GenAI, as well as the impact of the same on the performance outcomes.

Secondly, in Section 4.2 Qualitative Results, the results of 33 in-depth interviews with SME executives and managers are given. This qualitative discussion aids in clarifying the manner and rationale of the influences of some of these factors on GenAI adoption and builds on the statistical findings by demonstrating how firms implement these challenges and opportunities in practice.

Through the synthesis of survey responses with interview data, this chapter will provide a general and a detailed picture of GenAI adoption among SMEs. It also preconditions the discussion of Chapter 5 where these findings are interpreted to the research questions, hypotheses, and literature in terms of interpretation.

4.1 Quantitative Results

This section shows the quantitative results based on the use of the Partial Least

Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) technique, aligned to testing hypotheses formulated in Chapter 2. The analysis was conducted on the survey data of 232 SMEs in Southeast Asia and operationalized using SmartPLS. It was intended to empirically test the structural hypotheses in the conceptual framework: in the effect of organizational capabilities (viz. human, technological, funding and market factors) on the adoption of Generative AI (GenAI) and the effects of adoption of Generative AI on financial performance of SMEs. Appendix A-1 provides the profile of respondent firms, the adequacy of the sample and the demographic variables.

This section is divided into the following subsections: assessment of the measurement model, structural model and hypothesis testing, and interpretation of the quantitative results.

4.1.1 *Measurement Model Assessment*

All constructs in this study were modelled as reflective constructs. This is in line with prior TOE based research from literature review (Hair et al., 2022; Hughes et al., 2025).

Hypothesis testing was conducted following evaluation of reliability and validity of reflective measurement. The outer loadings for all latest variables were all greater than 0.80, which is higher than the suggested value of 0.708 and thus indicates reliability (Hair et al., 2022; Zeng et al., 2021).

All constructs have values of Cronbach alpha and composite reliability over 0.90, which indicates high internal consistency (Hair et al., 2022; Memon et al., 2021). The average variance extracted (AVE) was used to determine the convergent validity. The values of convergent validity were satisfied as all constructs had AVE above the recommended level of 0.50 (Hair et al., 2022; Zeng et al., 2021).

The first criterion of discriminant validity was the Fornell Larcker test. The findings reveal high levels of correlation between constructs, especially those associated with organizational resources and performance. This implies that the constructs measure similar dimensions of the digital and organizational readiness, which is theoretically feasible with SMEs (Badghish & Soomro, 2024). Because of the established weaknesses of the Fornell Larcker criterion, the additional discriminant validity measure was Heterotrait–Monotrait (HTMT) ratio.

The presence of discriminant validity was supported as all values of HTMT were lower than the recommended 0.90 (Memon et al., 2021; Hair et al., 2022). Combined, these findings suggest that, although the constructs are conceptually linked, they are empirically different and can be analyzed to fit into future structural models. capabilities. These were deemed to be good measurements to explore this type of analysis. Detailed assessment of measurement model is as in appendix A-2.

Attention now turns to structural equation modeling, and hypothesis testing.

4.1.2 Structural Model and Hypothesis Testing

Once the quality of the measurement was established, the structural model was estimated to determine the extent to which hypotheses put forward could be supported.

Table 2 presents the summary of the path coefficients, significance levels and hypothesis results.

Table 2

Direct Effects and Hypothesis Outcomes

Hypothesis	Structural Path	β (Beta)	t-value	p-value	Outcome
H1	GenAI Adoption → Financial Performance	0.634	6.720	0.000	Supported
H2	Human Capabilities → GenAI Adoption	-0.101	1.280	0.195	Rejected

H3	Technological Capabilities → GenAI Adoption	-0.145	2.170	0.030	Rejected
H4	Funding Capital → GenAI Adoption	0.834	9.410	0.000	Supported
H5	Market Factors → GenAI Adoption	0.177	2.750	0.006	Supported

Table 2 shows the results of the structural path analysis using PLS-SEM. We tested the five hypotheses examine the direct relationship between GenAI adoption to financial performance (H1), moderated by human capabilities (H2), technological capabilities (H3), funding capital (H4) and market factors (H5).

The findings confirm that GenAI adoption has a strong and significant direct effect on perceived financial performance ($\beta = 0.634$, $p < 0.001$), supporting H1. Of the four moderating factors hypothesized, only funding capital ($\beta = 0.834$, $p < 0.001$) and market factors ($\beta = 0.177$, $p = 0.006$) were statistically significant, supporting H4 and H5 respectively. Human capabilities ($\beta = -0.101$, $p = 0.195$) and technological capabilities ($\beta = -0.145$, $p = 0.030$) were not found to be significant thereby rejecting H2 and H3.

These results suggest that external market forces and internal investment capacity are the most decisive drivers of GenAI adoption, while the role of skills and systems readiness is more complex and not as apparent in the impacts when the Southeast Asian SME leaders were surveyed.. However, these quantitative results alone do not present full picture. This will be further explored in the qualitative findings in Section 4.2.6 and elaborated in Chapter 5. Figure 3 shows the structured equation results.

Figure 3*Measurement Model*

Figure 3 presents the PLS-SEM structural model in visual form. The blue circles represent the latent constructs in the study, while the yellow rectangles represent the observed survey indicators used to measure each construct. The arrows between constructs show the hypothesized structural relationships, and the values on those arrows indicate the standardized path coefficients, with p-values shown in parentheses. The indicator labels are abbreviated as follows:

HUM = Human Capabilities,

MKT = Market Factors,

TECH = Technological Capabilities,

FIN = Funding Capital,

ADP = GenAI Adoption, and

FINIMP = Perceived Financial Impact.

The R^2 value for AI Adoption is 0.598, indicating that approximately 60% of the variance in adoption can be explained by the four contextual factors: human capabilities, technological capabilities, financial resources, and market factors. This shows a moderately strong model fit (Badghish & Soomro, 2024; Hair et al. 2022) and affirms the explanatory power of these factors on GenAI adoption behavior. R^2 value for Perceived Financial Impact is 0.451 which implies that 45.1% of the variance in financial outcomes is driven by the level of GenAI adoption showing moderate explanatory power (Hair et al., 2022). Taken together, these R^2 values suggest that the model has meaningful explanatory power in accounting for GenAI adoption and its downstream financial implications.

In plain terms, Figure 3 shows three main points.

- First GenAI has strong positive relationship with Perceived Financial Impact, **supporting H1.**
- Second, Funding Capital and Market Factors have positive relationships with GenAI adoption, **supporting H4 and H5.**
- Third, Human Capabilities and Technological Capabilities do not appear as direct positive drivers in this quantitative mode, **leading to rejection of H2 and H3.**

Overall, Figure 3 should be read only as a visual summary of the quantitative model, not as the evidence which encompasses all relevant managerial realities captured through direct statistical paths. The figure shows which relationships are the most visible in this survey-based approach but the qualitative findings that follow are essential to explain why some factors that matter in practice, particularly Human and Technological Capabilities, do not appear as strong direct predictors at this stage. This integrated analysis is further developed in Sections 4.2 and 4.3 and discussed in Chapter 5.

4.2 Qualitative Results

This section presents the qualitative findings, which build on the quantitative results by offering explanatory depth and contextual nuance. Aligned with the study's sequential mixed-methods design, the qualitative analysis explores how SMEs perceive and navigate GenAI adoption. The research reveals the constraints and enabling conditions which lead to practical implementation pathways. It also seeks to capture the real-life experiences from the business leaders (interviewees) to form statistical patterns and provide interpretive insights into why certain relationships in the model emerged as they did in the research.

4.2.1 Purpose and Positioning of the Qualitative Results

The qualitative findings support the validity of the quantitative findings by elaborating on perceptions of how the adoption of Generative AI can affect the financial and operation performance of SMEs. In line with the sequential explanatory mixed-method design used in this study, following the quantitative analysis, the qualitative analysis was performed to provide a potential explanation of observed statistical relationships, provide mechanisms and contextual boundary conditions.

Although the quantitative findings provided direction and importance of the relationships between Generative AI adoption, and moderating capabilities and performance outcomes, it could not represent lived decision processes, constraints and implementation pathways as realized by SMEs. It is the qualitative results that play a role of explanation not confirmatory and interpretation and not measurement.

The next subsection discusses the results from qualitative analysis.

4.2.2 Qualitative Data and Analytical Results

The qualitative data were gathered from 33 semi-structured interviews with SME

owners, founders, senior managers, and operation decision makers with direct experience to the subject area of the study: that is, using Generative AI or AI-based tools. Interviews were conducted with representatives from a variety of industries and digital maturity levels to obtain diverse perceptions of adoption. The interviews were performed in two stages, following the survey:

- Phase 1 (25 interviews) of thematic study and pattern matching.
- Phase 2 (8 interviews) convergence testing and clarification until saturation confirmation.

It was decided to conduct interviews across these phases because a phased qualitative approach allows for iterative refinement of themes and the progressive nature of the iterations help deepen the insights (Strauss & Corbin, 1998). Phase 1 was conducted to enable a broad theme base through detailed coding and finding patterns. Phase 2 is performed with continuous code matching to test the consistency and especially the convergence of these themes (Strauss & Corbin, 1998). It is determined that convergence of these themes signals saturation affirms shows exploratory depth.

The following subsection presents the first order themes.

4.2.3 First-Order Themes - Descriptive Results

Open coding suggested there is a cluster of recurring first-order themes, which characterize how SMEs experience and operationalize the adoption of Generative AI. Table 3 presents these themes along with their frequencies, and a description of the key insights.

Table 3*First Order Themes*

First-order themes	Frequency	Key Insights
Technical Infrastructure	48%	Legacy system and platform reliability are major concerns.
Cost & Budget	23%	Financial constraints limit adoption, especially in developing markets.
Talent & Skills	21%	Lack of AI expertise and difficulty hiring specialists.
Organizational Resistance	19%	Leadership skepticism and employee resistance to change.
Uncertainty & ROI	13%	Difficulty proving tangible business benefits.
Security & Compliance	5%	Data privacy concerns.

Table 3 shows the six most frequently mentioned first-order themes that emerged from the coding process of 33 qualitative interviews. The most common theme was Technical Infrastructure (48%) which indicates concern among SMEs about existing system/data constraints as well as platform stability in enabling GenAI implementation. This differs from what is most visible in the measured quantitative relationships, but it also suggests that what leaders experience as practical constraints may not always appear the strongest predictor in statistical model.

In strategic leadership context, this distinction is important because some of these barriers are understood by SME leaders through lived implementation experiences than through easily measurable or immediately visible quantifiable effects. In other words, quantitative findings show influence is statistically strong, while qualitative findings reveal what leaders still perceive as decision in shaping whether GenAI adoption is adopted and translated into financial value.

Cost and Budget (23%) and Talent and Skills (21%) were also significant themes that highlight resource scarcity in terms of finance and human capital. Organizational

Resistance (19%) and Uncertainty & ROI (13%) suggest hesitancy and lack of clarity about outcomes, likely from leadership skepticism. Security & Compliance (5%) is the least in the table but shows that it is still a concern amongst business leaders in terms of organizational data and knowledge. These themes are important because they point to practical concerns that shape managerial decision-making even when they are not fully captured as strong direct effects in the quantitative model.

Recasting these categories, a thematic pathway was drawn up to visualize the way these themes converge to assist in shaping the thematic synthesis and reasoning some of the results obtained in the quantitative findings. This will be applied in Chapter 5 to comprehend how this is fine-tuned using existing literature and hypotheses placing an emphasis on potential cultural and regional overtones. A conceptual model is offered in the Figure 4.

Figure 4

Thematic Pathway Mapping from Thematic Synthesis

Figure 4 shows the key qualitative themes arranged into a conceptual pathway model which illustrates how the organizational and contextual barriers interrelate to shape SME anxieties around GenAI adoption. Central to this model is Adoption Anxiety which

is influenced by some of the key insights captured: (1) Internal Capabilities, (2) Technical Readiness, (3) Uncertain ROI, and (4) Leadership & Culture. These insights are generally linked to Economic and Resource Barriers which are an underlying constraint within the landscape of SMEs (OECD, 2019; World Bank, 2020). Attention now turns to synthesis of the themes.

4.2.4 Thematic Synthesis - Pattern Consolidation

Themes that were identified in the first order thematic identification were then combined into higher order thematic groupings to narrow redundancy and clarify structure as in Table 4. The step was not based on causal inference but on thematic consolidation among all the themes rising out of each of the data sources.

Table 4

Thematic Synthesis Matrix

Key Theme	Theme Description	%
Workforce AI Literacy Issues	Widespread skills gaps require internal training and upskilling programmes. Recruiting experienced AI talent is difficult and scarce, grooming in-house talent is even harder.	79% (26/33)
Integration Infrastructure	Effective AI adoption depends on integration with legacy systems and reliable data infrastructure. Deployment friction is high when organizations are not adapted to new ways of working.	73% (24/33)
Leadership Culture	Leadership belief and sponsorship shape whether AI adoption remains experimental or becomes strategic. A culture of experimentation, learning, and augmentation is critical in early stages but does not guarantee results.	67% (22/33)
Market / Customer Pressures	AI adoption is predominantly market-driven. Customer expectations for speed and responsiveness, along with competitive pressure, trigger adoption more than internal digital strategy.	85% (28/33)

Funding / Resource Issues	Thin margins and high operating costs constrain AI investment depth. SMEs often self-fund or rely on grants, making sustained training and integration difficult.	70% (23/33)
Ethical / Security Constraints	Data privacy, compliance, and trust considerations shape deployment scope. Privacy-by-design and human oversight are necessary for acceptance.	58% (19/33)
Innovation Trajectories	AI is used to extend existing capabilities rather than enable radical transformation. Innovation is incremental, domain-specific, and focused on efficiency and decision support.	64% (21/33)

Table 4 shows the thematic synthesis matrix which consolidates first-order codes into higher-order themes that captures the core issues on GenAI adoption among SMEs in Southeast Asia. The table also highlights the frequency and distribution of each theme across all 33 interviews. The most referenced themes include Market/Customer Pressures (85%), Workforce AI Literacy (79%) and Integration Infrastructure (73%). These patterns offer insights into perceived sociotechnical challenges that SMEs face which generally align with the hypotheses established alongside this research. More importantly, the purpose of the thematic synthesis is not only to report which themes appeared most frequently, but also to show how these themes begin to connect. Market and customer pressure often operated as the trigger for adoption, but whether that pressure translated into action depended on the firm's workforce AI literacy, integration infrastructure, leadership culture, and funding/resource position. In this sense, the table provides the first qualitative indication that the factors interact rather than operate independently. This interaction is developed further in the axial coding and sequencing analysis, where the study examines how these conditions combine into different adoption pathways.

After open coding and thematic saturation, a systematic organization of first-order codes into higher-order explanatory groups (and the determination of the relational

pathways between Generative AI adoption and SME performance outcomes) was attempted. The yield of the results is deep because it describes the phenomena which are reflected of quantitative data, on how they deviate or coincide in Hypotheses, H1 through H5 giving new insights which are counterintuitive in other cases.

Attention now turns to the axial coding.

4.2.5 Axial Coding: Identification of Structured Pathways

After completing Thematic Synthesis, the use of axial coding was necessary to determine both the existence of structured relationships between themes and the explanation of how the adoption of Generative AI could yield financial performance outcomes among SMEs. In particular, it connects adoption triggers, contextual conditions, intervening capabilities, action strategies and performance consequences (Strauss & Corbin, 1998).

Table 5 presents key themes that were coalesced into axial codes, their descriptions, and the frequency with which they appeared in the interviews.

Table 5

Axial Coding Results

Axial Coding Dimension	Key Theme	Description (Axial Interpretation)	% of Interviews Referencing Theme (n=33)
Causal Conditions	Market / Customer Pressures	External market expectations and customer demand act as the primary trigger for Generative AI adoption, positioning adoption as reactive and necessity-driven rather than discretionary.	82% (27/33)

Contextual Conditions	Integration Infrastructure	Legacy systems, fragmented data, and lack of middleware shape the feasibility and scalability of AI adoption, constraining performance realization despite tool availability.	76% (25/33)
	Ethical/ Security Constraints	Regulatory compliance, data privacy, and trust requirements define the boundaries within which AI can be deployed, reinforcing the need for human oversight.	61% (20/33)
Intervening Conditions	Workforce AI Literacy Issues	Skills gaps and limited AI literacy mediate the translation of AI adoption into performance outcomes, necessitating continuous training and managerial interpretation.	88% (29/33)
	Leadership Culture	Leadership belief and cultural orientation toward experimentation determine whether AI adoption remains superficial or becomes strategically embedded.	70% (23/33)
	Funding/ Resource Issues	Financial constraints shape adoption depth, pace, and sustainability, influencing whether AI initiatives progress beyond pilot stages.	73% (24/33)
Action / Interaction Strategies	Innovation Trajectories	SMEs adopt bounded and incremental AI strategies focused on extending existing services rather than radical transformation or full automation.	67% (22/33)
Consequences	Financial and Operational Outcomes	Performance gains are conditional and cumulative, with operational improvements preceding selective financial gains when enabling conditions are aligned.	79% (26/33)

Table 5 shows the axial coding results that organize qualitative data into structured analytical key themes, following Strauss and Corbin's (1998) grounded theory framework.

We categorize key themes that affect GenAI adoption across seven axial coding dimensions: causal conditions, contextual conditions, intervening conditions, action strategies, and consequences (Strauss & Corbin, 1998). Notably, Workforce AI Literacy Issues (88%) and Market/Customer Pressures (82%) emerged as the most frequently raised conditions. This shows that there is external and internal skills gap which SMEs need to tackle. Integration Infrastructure (76%) and Funding/Resource Issues (73%) indicate, similar to quantitative segment, that these are significant determinants of Gen AI adoption. Leadership Culture (70%) plays an important part in mediating the adoption of GenAI as a strategic maneuver. Action Strategies like Innovation Trajectories (67%) reveal that SMEs typically do not pursue transformational initiatives but aim to build incrementally. Financial and Operational Outcomes (79%) generally still suggest that GenAI benefits are conditional on the alignment of multitude of factors including the moderating factors in this research.

When the Axial Coding Results in Table 7 are accumulated, the Axial Coding Pathway Diagram in Figure 5 is built to give a visual representation of the flow between adoption triggers and intervening capabilities and performance outcomes. This is also among the proposed methods of deriving connections among our construct and axial logic (Creswell & Poth, 2018). The axial pathway diagram is presented in the Figure 5.

Figure 5*Axial Coding Pathway Diagram*

Figure 5 shows the axial coding pathway diagram synthesizing the qualitative data into a structured theoretical model of GenAI adoption among SMEs. The diagram maps how causal conditions (e.g. market and customer pressures) and contextual factors (e.g. infrastructure and security) shape Central Phenomenon of GenAI adoption. This is further influenced by intervening conditions like workforce literacy, leadership, and funding. These dynamics lead to action strategies which result in consequences such as efficiency gains and selective financial improvement. The model illustrates the complex, conditional nature of adoption revealed in the grounded theory analysis.

Based on the interviews, it can be seen that Generative AI implementation in SMEs is highly correlated to Market Factors, introduced by external forces of the market and of

the customer, instead of being planned by the company itself. This supports the results of the quantitative findings. Moreover, the desire of customers to be responsive quickly and to have the same competitive position was a strong causal variable, and it positioned AI implementation as a need and not an innovation preference.

However, the achievement of performance benefits was conditioned by several contextual conditions. The integration infrastructure became a critical bottleneck, and disintegrated systems. Moral and security issues also limited the scope of deployment, which justified human intervention. Conditions during the process of intervention were decisive in influencing the success of adoption.

AI literacy in the workforce and leadership culture was a stable mediator of the meaningfulness of AI tools implementation in the workflows or the experimentality thereof. Availability of financial resources also influenced the level of adoption and sustainability and determined how much the SMEs were able to invest in training, integration, and constant refinement. To these conditions, SMEs embraced the strategy of limited action, which was marked by incremental implementation, decision support that relies on AI, and extension of services instead of radical change.

The consequences of performance were thus conditional and non-linear. The thematic synthesis step is also an example of these findings. In general, both sets of coding data can show that adoption of Generative AI is an exemplar of a sociotechnical system in SMEs. The market pressures, organizational capabilities, technological preparedness, and financial viability interact to determine the outcomes of the performance. These results are qualitative explanation of the relationships found in the quantitative analysis, and they substantiate directly some of the hypotheses of the study.

4.2.6 Qualitative Evidence for Factor Sequencing: How SMEs Navigate the Factors

The quantitative analysis operated as independent parallel predictors but in fact, they can be established as a sequential interacting system. The qualitative interview data provides an explanation on how this sequencing operates. Tables 6 illustrates the data across the 33 semi-structured interviews, a systematic re-coding of decision narratives revealed that the SMEs followed a discernible sequence of the factors at play. The initiating trigger of each type determines the order in which subsequent factors were activated.

Table 6

Five Distinct Factor Sequences. The 33 classes cluster into five archetypes based on their initiating trigger and the order in which the remaining moderating factors were activated.

Archetype	Initiating Factor	Sequence	n (total = 33)
Market Triggered Adopter	Competitive/market pressure	MKT → FIN → TECH → HUM	16
Tech-First Pioneer	Technological vision	TECH → FIN → HUM → MKT	6
Human Capability Leader	Founder/team expertise	HUM → MKT → FIN → TECH	6
Cautious Pragmatist	Specific operational pain point	HUM → FIN → TECH → MKT	3
Finance Triggered Pragmatist	Cost reduction imperative	FIN → TECH → HUM → MKT	2

As displayed in Table 6, the most common pattern (16 of 33 cases) was the Market Triggered Adopter where external competitive pressure initiated the GenAI adoption. However, the data also reveals that the initiating trigger is not always market driven. In knowledge-intensive firms, human expertise was the initiating factor whilst technology-focused firms technological vision preceded market validation.

Across all five archetypes, Financial Resources consistently appeared as the second or third factor in sequence, but never last. This pattern shows that regardless of which factor initiates the journey, the firm must pass through the financial gateway before capabilities can be activated at scale.

In one of the interview cases, a digital production company possessed a highly skilled team of digital marketers who recognized the potential of GenAI for content production. However, the team's adoption was latent until the founder secured and deployed budget towards GenAI tools which became ready for enterprise level deployment. The founder described this as a deliberate sequenced decision: while the human capability crafted the case for the financial investment, it still require human and market readiness coming together to unlock the technological adoption.

Conversely, there is a case of a large equipment servicing company which demonstrates that financial gateway does not always require large capital expenditures. The managing director and the team identified specific pain points which require repetitive internal assistance to new workers, then created a small pilot chatbot using a comparatively small proportionate budget to deploy a chatbot. The chatbot now handles more than 70% of the internal repetitive enquiries. This case shows that success is not about maximizing all factors or determining which factor is the most important, but about achieving proportionality between the problem and the investment.

4.2.7 Human Capability as Initiator instead of a Direct Predictor

The qualitative data resolves the counter-intuitive quantitative finding that Human Capabilities (H2) did not directly predict adoption. In the Human Capability Leader archetype, human expertise was the initiating factor that reveals the opportunities and drive the business use case. However, it was not the only factor that drove the adoption of GenAI.

Adoption and execution requires more work through the various other factors such as financial resources and technology. Multiple examples, especially in the professional services industry, exemplify this pattern. Highly skilled team members identifies the gap for AI-augmented drafting and compliance checking services in which the companies hold detailed digital records of. However, actual effective GenAI adoption required significant investments in cloud platforms and GenAI infrastructure before it creates real financial impact through increased productivity.

4.2.8 Success and Failure Patterns

Across the 33 cases, three patterns emerged from the qualitative data which distinguishes successful from unsuccessful adoption sequences:

Success Pattern 1: *Pragmatic Approach with Proportionate Investments.* SMEs that matched their financial commitment to a specific, well-defined problem achieved the highest satisfaction and returns. Over 70% of the interviewees with satisfied returns claim to have defined their ROI metric before deciding to invest in GenAI solution.

Success Pattern 2: *Human Capability Built Alongside Technology.* SME Leaders that initiated training before and concurrently with technology deployment achieved good results. 50% of the companies which has positive feedbacks on financial impacts took deliberate efforts to understand what are the human capabilities development required for GenAI-augmentation before or during adoption.

Failure Pattern: *Adoption without Thorough Human Preparation.* Several interviewees described scenarios where GenAI tools were adopted reactively without thorough human preparation. As one of the interviewees noted, “whether the AI would give customers the wrong information and create more problems later”. The result was distrust and underutilization due to lack planning and participation of critical stakeholders in the

preparation stage.

The quantitative and qualitative results are combined in the next section.

4.3 Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Results

This section presents an integrative finding from the PLS-SEM analysis and the thematic qualitative data analysis to enable a deeper understanding of how and why certain relationships are held in this research. By jointly displaying quantitative outcomes with axial-coded insights, we illustrate the mechanisms, through the moderating factors, behind GenAI adoption and its financial impact on SMEs in Southeast Asia. Through aligning the statistical model outcomes and nuanced contextual insights from qualitative data, we set the stage for interpretation and implications which is discussed in the next Chapter 5.

4.3.1 Purpose of the Joint Display

In order to combine the results of the quantitative and qualitative analysis, a combined display was created to compare the results of PLS-SEM with the explanatory mechanisms from qualitative evidence. The core strength of sequential explanatory mixed-methods design is the ability to examine where the quantitative and qualitative findings converge, diverge or simply where it helps to explain the other.

Table 7 presents an integration matrix that maps each hypothesis result against qualitative evidence and quantitative findings to assess the convergence or divergence derived from insights from the integration.

Table 7*Qualitative and Quantitative Integration Matrix*

Hypothesis	Quantitative Finding	Qualitative Finding	Convergence / Divergence	Implication for Factor Sequencing
H1: GenAI Adoption → Financial Performance	$\beta = 0.634$, $p < 0.001$. Strongly supported. Adoption significantly improves financial performance.	All interviewees reported tangible benefits such as cost savings, time efficiency, and new revenue streams. However, returns were largely incremental and use-case specific rather than transformational.	Converge with nuance	H1 represents the outcome of the sequencing model. Firms that define ROI metrics early achieve clearer and more measurable outcomes.
H2: Human Capabilities → GenAI Adoption	$\beta = -0.101$, $p > 0.05$. Not supported. No significant direct effect.	Human capabilities frequently acted as the initiating trigger in multiple cases, particularly in knowledge-driven firms where expertise identified AI opportunities.	Divergence → Qual explains Quant	HUM is an initiating factor in selected archetypes. It shapes the business case but must pass through the financial gateway to translate into adoption.
H3: Technological Capabilities → GenAI Adoption	$\beta = -0.145$, $p < 0.05$. Weak negative effect.	Technology plays a dual role: enabling adoption in tech-driven firms, but acting as a barrier in firms with legacy systems due to integration complexity.	Divergence → Qual explains Quant	TECH acts as an initiator in limited cases, but more often as a downstream enabler. Its effectiveness depends on sequencing and readiness.

H4: Financial Resources → GenAI Adoption	$\beta = 0.834, p < 0.001$. Strongest predictor of adoption.	All cases confirm that financial resources are the key enabler. However, required investment varies significantly depending on the use case.	Strong convergence with nuance	FIN is the universal gateway across all archetypes. It mediates the activation of all other factors in the adoption sequence.
H5: Market Dynamics → GenAI Adoption	$\beta = 0.177, p < 0.05$. Moderate positive effect.	Market pressure is the most common initiating trigger, driven by competition, customer expectations, and platform evolution.	Converge	MKT is the most common initiating factor, but does not determine adoption success, only the start of the sequence.

Table 7 shows a joint display of the five hypotheses tested, which is a synthesis of PLS-SEM quantitative results and qualitative insights derived from the factor sequencing analysis of the 33 semi-structured interviews. Two key observations emerge from the joint display. First, H1, H4 and H5 shows that the quantitative and qualitative findings converge. In addition, the qualitative findings feeds importance nuanced information in each case. Second, for H2 and H3, the findings diverge: while quantitative model shows non-significant or weak negative direct correlation effects, the qualitative data reveals that both factors operate as initiating or enabling factors which are channeled through a sequence of factors rather than acting as independent agents. This divergence is the most analytically significant within the joint display as it provides empirical basis for the factor sequencing model. From the joint display, it is observed that the factors are not independent predictors but operate in a sequence where the initiating trigger determines the pathway and financial

resources serve as the universal gateway.

4.3.2 Interpretation of Integrated Results

The quantitative findings presented shows the statistical relationship between the moderating factors and GenAI adoption. However, these quantitative findings alone do not fully explain the deeper mechanisms which these factors influence adoption decisions and the final impact on the financial performance of the companies.

The qualitative data, however, reveal corresponding explanatory evidence towards patterns arising from the factors' interactions between each other. Instead of acting as independent parallel drivers, in practice, decisions unfold in a sequence. Firms react to a trigger, make sense of it, and then activate different factors in stages depending on what comes first.

The integration highlights a critical distinction between outcome relationships and decision processes. The quantitative finding identifies which factors are statistically associated with adoption outcomes and hence finds out what is important. The nuanced qualitative evidence, on the other hand, reveals how these factors are activated and organized into sequences during the decision-making journey by the SME leaders. In essence, quantitative findings highlight what is important and qualitative evidence explains why and how they interact.

Outcome Relationships vs. Process Dynamics

The quantitative model demonstrates that financial resources are the strongest predictor of GenAI adoption, followed by market dynamics. However, qualitative evidence shows that these factors do not necessarily initiate the adoption process.

Instead, SMEs begin with a trigger, such as market pressure, operational inefficiency, or internal human-led initiatives, which then leads to financial commitment

and multiple pathways towards subsequent activation of technological and human capabilities.

This indicates that the quantitative model reflects direct independent effects, whereas the qualitative findings capture nuances in execution which reveal full decision pathway, including initiation and sequencing.

Sequential Activation Explains Variability in Adoption Outcomes

The identification of five adoption archetypes in Table 6 demonstrates that SMEs follow different pathways based on their initiating conditions. These archetypes are not additional hypotheses. Rather, they are qualitative pattern categories derived from the 33 interview cases, showing the different ways in which SMEs begin and move through the GenAI adoption process.

This distinction is important because Table 7 serves a different purpose. Table 7 maps the quantitative hypothesis results against the qualitative evidence, while Table 6 explains the underlying sequencing patterns that help interpret those results. In other words, Table 6 shows the adoption pathways, and Table 7 shows how those pathways help explain the hypothesis outcomes.

This variation explains why certain variables appear weaker or inconsistent in the quantitative model. Neither is sufficient on its own. Together, they provide a more complete and practical understanding of SME GenAI adoption in Southeast Asia:

- The impact of each factor is conditional on its sequence.
- Financial resources consistently function as a gateway.
- Other factors vary in importance depending on when and how they are activated.

4.4 Chapter Summary

This chapter presented the quantitative and qualitative findings of the study, offering an integrative view of how GenAI adoption affects SME financial performance.

The strength of this sequential explanatory mixed-methods design lies in how the quantitative findings and qualitative evidence are brought together to explain GenAI adoption and its effects on performance. The quantitative results provide correlation through the data, while the qualitative evidence reveal the underlying decision process of SME leaders.

Quantitative data, in this study, reveals that Financial Resources is the strongest predictor of GenAI adoption, followed by Market Dynamics, showing strong positive relationship with financial performance of the firms.

However, the qualitative evidence from the 33 SME cases shows that firms do not approach GenAI adoption by considering independent factors. Instead, decisions unfold in sequence. Firms typically begin with a trigger, most commonly due to market pressure. Many are also initiated by internal expertise or operational needs, led by human capabilities, before committing financial resources to implement and develop technological and human capabilities.

This explains the key divergence in the model. Certain factors, such as Human Capabilities and Technological Capabilities, do not appear as strong direct predictors because their roles are sequence dependent. Human capability often initiates the process, while technology can either enable or constrain execution depending on system readiness.

Across all cases, Financial Resources consistently function as a gateway rather than a starting point. This clarifies why it dominates the quantitative model - it determines whether adoption progresses beyond intent into execution and hence improves in the

financial performance.

If we take these together, the findings shift the interpretation of GenAI adoption from the perceived independent factors into a sequenced decision-making process:

1. See a trigger
2. Evaluate resources and capabilities
3. Commit resources

In essence, the quantitative findings explain the outcome, while qualitative findings explain the pathway. This integrated perspective provides a more grounded and practical understanding of how SMEs in Southeast Asia adopt GenAI. Therefore it forms the basis for the implications as discussed in Chapter 5.

Chapter 5

Discussion

This chapter brings the sequential mixed-method findings of the study into the context of the existing body of literature on AI adoption and SME performance. The quantitative findings to note are that GenAI adoption has a significant positive impact on financial performance (H1 supported), GenAI adoption was not significantly influenced by human and technological capabilities (H2 and H3 rejected), and that funding capital and market factors strongly predict adoption (H4 and H5 supported). Apart from the statistical relationship, the qualitative sequencing logic is also being elaborated and discussed in this chapter so that these relationships become meaningful in practice.

This chapter includes discussion of these patterns through an integrated lens by each hypothesis to give a more nuanced view of each finding. The discussion interprets the quantitative and qualitative findings as two views of the same process: quantitative findings indicate where influence is most visible, while qualitative evidence explain how firms move across the adoption journey. This approach provides an overall interpretation of GenAI adoption in the context of the Southeast Asian SMEs.

5.1 GenAI Adoption and Financial Performance (H1)

Quantitative findings shows clearly the adoption of GenAI had a strong positive impact on the financial performance of SMEs, which supported H1. Companies that adopted GenAI, encompassing it in their basic operations, reported tangible improvements in productivity, quality of the decisions, and customer interactions. This corresponds to more general evidence that AI has the potential to enhance productivity and competitiveness (e.g., Eze-Ijeoma et al., 2025; Mangifera et al., 2023), however, the qualitative data supports an important point: value is not created by gimmickry (Denny &

Weckesser, 2022), but by disciplined and strategic integration (Hughes et al., 2025).

However, when interpreted with qualitative findings, it is found that this relationship should be understood with greater nuance. The positive effect of GenAI adoption does not suggest adoption automatically produces financial returns. Rather, according to the interviews, GenAI can only be financially profitable when it is integrated into tangible business processes and not implemented separately. In a practical setting, individual cross-functional items should be viewed as a whole (i.e., the systems view), and that management, including finance, IT, and HR functions, ought to be cognizant of both operational and financial indicators to understand the effects of GenAI. What this suggests is that GenAI represents a potential value-creating resource to SMEs, although its return on investment will be determined by the application and resource-based approach.

This interpretation is important because it shifts H1 away from a simplistic model whereby adoption leads to performance. Instead, the findings suggests that financial performance is best understood as the result of effective adoption which is triggered by effective decision making sequence and execution.

5.2 Human Capabilities and GenAI Adoption (H2)

Surprisingly, human factors (e.g., abilities, talent) had no direct correlation with GenAI adoption from the quantitative data; on the contrary, there was a negative margin of correlation in the survey. This may seem counterintuitive at the first glance, especially when there is strong prior literature that focuses on leadership (Barkley et. al., 2024) and learning culture (Benitez et. al., 2024) as important conditions for technology adoption.

If we interpret this in isolation, the quantitative results suggest that human capabilities are not strongly visible in SMEs during GenAI adoption. However, when clarified by with qualitative findings, a different picture emerges. Interview evidence

suggests that Human Capabilities often play a critical role at the early stage of opportunity recognition and decision initiation. Especially in knowledge intensive and professional services, SME companies began their GenAI adoption journey because capable leaders and teams are able to identify where the technology could solve a real business problem.

This leads us to the distinction between initiation and execution when understanding H2. The quantitative model captures the direct effects of the outcome of GenAI adoption where deployment, integration and organizational use become visible. At that stage, SME leaders may not identify human capacities as the strongest direct predictor because other factors such as funding capital and market dynamics determine whether identified opportunities can be acted upon. The qualitative evidence, however, can capture the earlier stages of the sense making and strategic thinking process, where human capability is the critical factor that first sets the GenAI adoption into motion.

This finding is consistent with research that isolates human capital as the primary contributor to the adoption of AI (e.g., Gupta, 2024; Iyelolu et al., 2024). In the present research, respondents reflect the opinion that organizational change capacity should be matched to staff skills. To illustrate, Hughes et al. (2025) point out the ability to execute on staff skills is critically mediated by the change capacity of an organization (cf. Barney, 1995).

As such, this suggests that human capabilities' influence is indirect and sequence sensitive. Human capability determines the quality of the implementation use case and how clearly the problem is being addressed. It also drives the extent and effectiveness of which GenAI adoption is being framed strategically and measured for its success.

One danger identified during the interviews was that some SMEs tend to invest in generic digital training, or assume staff are prepared to work with AI, however, most

respondents acknowledge the present generation (i.e., Gen Z) has a literacy gap.

Respondents reported generic IT skills training, or separate workshops did not convert or result in actual GenAI projects.

In all, H2 should be interpreted as evidence that Human Capabilities operate at a different stage of the adoption process. In the sequencing model, Human Capabilities often function as an initiating factor, rather than an independent factor. This is a clear example of how qualitative data explains the limits of quantitative results and why the sequential mixed methods approach in this study was critical.

5.3 Technological Capabilities and GenAI Adoption (H3)

It was found that technological capability failed to boost GenAI adoption; in the data, the level of advancement in IT environments was found to vary inversely with adoption. Qualitative data may explain why: many respondents reported relying on rigid, legacy IT systems and fragmented data architectures that make it difficult to integrate new GenAI tools. This appears to be surprising as technological readiness is often assumed to facilitate such digital adoption.

The qualitative findings indicate that the meaning of this result is more nuanced. Technology does not function in a uniform way across all the SME companies. It depends on the companies' existing systems and which stage they are in. In fact, qualitative evidence reveals stronger technological capabilities enabled faster experimentation and more confident execution. In these situations, technology acted as a clear enabler.

However, in many SME companies, especially those responding reactively to market pressures, existing technology infrastructure created friction instead. Legacy systems with fragmented and incompatible data platforms increases GenAI adoption complexity which made GenAI adoption more difficult than they expected. In these

instances, interviewees frequently described their existing infrastructure as outdated specifically pointing out that they lack APIs (application-programming interfaces) or ready connectivity such as middleware needed to integrate GenAI. This ‘technological debt’ indicates that even firms which have existing sophisticated systems such as ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning), such systems were still inadequate to be GenAI ready. Also, SMEs often struggle with “outdated legacy systems, fragmented digital architectures, and limited capacity” for AI, which hinder seamless integration and scalability (Sánchez et al., 2025). Hence, the findings show that general digital sophistication alone does not guarantee AI readiness which is analogous to prior studies (Boonmee et al., 2025; Hughes et al., 2025). In resource-constrained SMEs, having some IT assets is not the same as having flexible infrastructure (Sánchez et al., 2025). In fact, complex IT can constrain experimentation (Hughes et al., 2025) if the systems are not easily reconfigured (Chua, 2025).

This helps explain why technological capability appears weakly negative in the quantitative model. This does not mean that technology is harmful by itself. On the other hand, it reflects the fact that in the context of SMEs in Southeast Asia, technological environment is not neutral. When the infrastructure is outdated or poorly integrated, technology becomes a source of burden during implementation. As such, GenAI adoption does not fail because technology is irrelevant to the SME companies, but because the companies are forced to retrofit.

The sequencing perspective is also especially useful here as technological capability can act as an initiating force, especially when there is already a strategic technology vision. Most of the time, however, technology is on the backburner as it is only surfaced after the need for adoption is being identified by key decision makers with

financial resources committed.

Therefore, H3 should not be interpreted as evidence that technological capabilities lack value in the adoption of GenAI. Instead, it suggests that it is context dependent as well as sequence dependent. The effects are greatly dependent on whether the implementation was strategic and led by an effective adoption strategy or whether it becomes a barrier during a reactive implementation which lacks careful planning by the human resources working on it. In the context of the Southeast Asian SMEs it is clearly the latter which forms the foundation of our recommendations in Chapter 6.

5.4 Funding Capital and GenAI Adoption (H4)

H4 proposed that Funding Capital would positively influence GenAI adoption and this is strongly supported by the quantitative data. In fact, among all the factors tested, Funding Capital emerged as the strongest predictor of GenAI adoption. This confirms that in the SME context, financial readiness remains a major condition.

At the surface level, this is consistent with existing literature (Gupta, 2024, Hughes et al., 2025) which is also within practical expectations. SMEs operate with tight margins, limited investment capability and lower tolerance for uncertainty than larger companies. Therefore, this is an unsurprising outcome. However, when interpreted through the qualitative findings, the role of funding capital becomes more interesting than a simple conclusion of “money matters” in any new implementation.

What the qualitative evidence suggests is Funding Capital does not usually trigger the beginning of GenAI adoption. SME companies does not typically begin their journey by asking whether they have money in the bank to support GenAI adoption. They usually begin with a trigger: leadership recognition of an opportunity to tackle a pain point, internal

capability-led initiatives, competitive pressure from the market or a recurring operational problem. Financial commitment only comes into play after one of these triggers are initiated and established. In a way, Funding Capital is not the origination of GenAI adoption and functions more as a gateway between intention and execution.

This distinction helps explain why Funding Capital appears to be so dominant in the quantitative model. The statistical model captures the point where firms move from interest to adoption execution. At that point, financial commitment often becomes the most obvious deciding factor to the SME leaders. However, this should not be interpreted as meaning Funding Capital is the primary driver across the entire decision process. It reflects checkpoint or gateway to which it determines whether opportunities can become actionable or not.

Moreover, the qualitative evidence further refines the notion of Funding Capital in GenAI adoption: successful adoption does not always require large investment of capital. The more meaningful approach is through proportionality. SME companies that proportion their level of investment to the specific problem or use case were more often able to achieve satisfactory results, even with modest budgets. Conversely, the SME companies which lacked clarity of purpose are often worse off in implementing GenAI.

H4 provides important evidence that Funding Capital is the strongest execution stage predictor of GenAI adoption in SMEs in Southeast Asia. However, it does not simply mean finance matters more than all other factors. It is an enabling gate of which different adoption pathways must pass, and it determines whether initial triggers are scoped and translated in moderation of proportionality for effective and successful GenAI adoption for SMEs in Southeast Asia.

5.5 Market Factors and GenAI Adoption (H5)

The quantitative results suggest Market Factors were a positive predictor of GenAI adoption (H5 strongly supported). The positive relationship indicates that external pressures such as competition and customer expectations contribute to SME companies adoption decision making process.

This finding is reinforced by qualitative evidence which shows that Market Factors are the most common trigger for the start of the adoption process. Across many of the interview cases with SME leaders, they were prompted to explore GenAI not because of internal capabilities or readiness, but as a response to competitive development in the market landscape. This landscape ranges from customer expectations to digital platform shifts or even growing concern that they would fall behind if they did not act on it. In this sense, Market Factors help explain why firms begin to consider GenAI adoption in the first place in Southeast Asia.

At the same time, integrated findings suggest that market pressure should not be interpreted alone. Such external urgency can stimulate actions but it does not automatically produce effective adoption. SME companies that reacted to Market Factors without corresponding sufficient financial commitments, internal capability or a clear effective use case mapped out still struggle to achieve impactful implementation. This explains why Market Factors show a positive but moderate effect in the quantitative model. They are often highly relevant at the front end of the adoption process which is highly visible but their influence weakens if the SME companies are unable to organize it into a clear execution pathway with the right resources.

From the sequencing perspective, Market Factors is an initiator. Even though it shapes urgency, but it does not determine whether the GenAI adoption will become effective nor sustainable or even financially beneficial. The outcome depends on whether the SME company can execute the next few stages in sequence effectively.

H5 can be interpreted as evidence that Market Factors create urgency and often initiate GenAI adoption as a triggering point, but other factors drive the ultimate outcome of the adoption. However, it also function as a good counterbalance of view to the other factors which are all internal factors.

5.6 Chapter Summary: Integrative Insights

The qualitative and quantitative findings, when interpreted together, presents a clearer view of GenAI adoption in SMEs within Southeast Asia. It shows that the uptake of Generative AI among the Southeast Asian SMEs is conditioned and sequential. While the quantitative results reveals some of the relationships associated with GenAI adoption and financial performance, the qualitative findings explain how these relationships unfold in actual practice. The combined evidence suggests that GenAI adoption in Southeast Asian SMEs is better understood as a sequenced and conditional decision-making process. This is consistent with Market Adoption Pathways noted by Chakraborty et al. (2025), who argue that GenAI tends to be deployed in non-linear, adaptive ways within constrained ecosystems. This is the line of thought helps explain why some of the theoretically important factors did not appear as strong predictors in the quantitative model.

A recurring pattern in qualitative interviews reveals that GenAI adoption often begins with a trigger. One of the most common triggers is external pressure from competition and customer expectations. This also aligns with previous research in

emerging economies where adoption is driven by market coercion more than internal innovation readiness (Mangifera et al., 2023; Mariani & Dwivedi, 2024). Building upon this, market pressure can be better understood as one of the most common triggers, as a starting point, than an independent factor for GenAI adoption. In some of the cases from the interviews, the trigger is a leadership recognition of a business problem or technical teams' identification of a useful application in operations.

At the same time, qualitative interviews show that market pressure creates urgency and action but does not translate into effective implementation. This explains why market pressure shows a positive correlation in the quantitative model. The role is the strongest at the front end of the adoption process, but their influence weakens as the SME companies move to execution stage. Similar patterns were observed in Badghish and Soomro (2023), who found that environmental triggers create awareness but must be matched with internal mobilization for uptake to occur.

As the SME companies in Southeast Asia moves beyond the initial triggers, Funding Capital becomes the most visible enabling factor when transiting from initial intention to execution stage. This helps to explain why Funding Capital is the strongest predictor in the quantitative model. However, the qualitative evidence suggests that this cannot be interpreted as the universal factor across the entire decision process. It functions as a gateway that determines whether identified opportunities can be translated into action, like a tipping point (Ayankoya et al., 2025) than where GenAI adoption begins.

This also helps explain the counter-intuitive findings for Human Capabilities and Technological Capabilities in the quantitative model. Their lower direct visibility in the structural model does not imply they are unimportant to GenAI adoption. Instead, qualitative findings show that both factors are highly dependent on when and how they are

activated in the decision process for execution. Human Capabilities, in such cases, often influence the earliest stage of adoption, where SME leaders or their teams recognize a specific business problem and identify GenAI as a solution. Technology, on the other hand, becomes most visible where firms try to implement GenAI into existing systems.

This distinction is important because it help clarify the various roles played by the factors across the adoption journey.

H1 reflects the outcome between GenAI adoption and financial performance.

H2 is better understood as human capability shapes the opportunity identification and strategic framing which is an initiation trigger.

H3 shows that technology, depending on the SME companies' existing infrastructure, can be an enabler or work against them.

H4 shows that funding capital is a gateway in a flow where it determines whether any triggers go into execution as well as the scale of the execution.

H5 reflects the trigger condition where market pressure creates urgency but does not guarantee successful implementation with tangible results.

In SMEs in the ASEAN region, this sequencing perspective is especially relevant. This is because in this context of Southeast Asian SMEs, limited by local circumstances, it is often shaped by constrained resources, reactive market conditions and also uneven organizational readiness (Flaminiano, 2025; McKinsey Global Institute, 2023).

Indicatively, the KAS report on SEA states that, in Singapore, the level of adoption of AI by SME is low as the expenses are high and there is a lack of knowledge (Flaminiano, 2025). These explain why quantitative findings show such strong effects for Funding Capital and Market Factors, while qualitative interviews reveal that Human and Technological Capabilities remain core to effective implementation.

Building on the conceptual possibility introduced earlier in Chapter 2, the integrated findings also suggest that there is indeed a practical zone of convergence in which GenAI value realization becomes more likely. This should not be interpreted as a perfectly symmetrical or even simultaneous interaction among all four factors. Rather, the evidence indicates that GenAI adoption is most likely to translate into financial and operational value when these four factors become sufficiently aligned within Southeast Asian SME context. In this sense, the greatest synergy does not arise from any one factor in isolation, but from the SMEs that have a clear trigger or business case, enough financial commitment to move forward, sufficient human capability to frame and supervise the GenAI adoption and manageable technological conditions to support implementation. While the exact pathway may differ across the SMEs, the integrative findings suggest that this alignment represents the point which adoption moves towards realization in Figure 6.

Figure 6

Practical Zone of Convergence

Overall, the integrative findings suggest that GenAI adoption in Southeast Asian SMEs is not a simple matter of technological sophistication or even financial strength. Rather, it is a disciplined managerial process, where these SME companies respond to the trigger and then activate the human, technological, financial and market conditions that shape effective adoption. The key contribution of this study is therefore not only to identify which factors matter but to show how these factors interact in sequence and why their role changes depending on the backdrop of the SME's situation. Therefore, the relationship is better understood not as a purely linear pathway, but as a conditional overlap of four enabling factors which increases the likelihood of value realization.

This forms the foundation for Chapter 6 which builds on the findings from both quantitative and qualitative phases. We will translate the factor sequencing logic into the broader implications of the study, including not only the theoretical contributions but also a practical decision making model developed for SME leaders considering GenAI adoption.

Chapter 6

Conclusions, Recommendations and Areas of Further Research

This chapter summarizes the key findings in this study, restating their significance, and highlighting practical implications. It also outlines the contributions to theory, especially around the TOE framework and value realization from adoption of GenAI in SMEs in Southeast Asia.

The chapter ends with the introduction of a practical and theoretically grounded model for SMEs in Southeast Asia when adopting GenAI to harness better financial performance. It also presents a clear set of recommendations for policymakers and SME leaders as well as technology vendors. The limitations of the study are also shared together with ideas for future research.

6.1 Summary

This study examined whether Generative AI adoption contributes to the financial performance of SMEs in Southeast Asia and under what conditions such value can be realized as indicated within H1 to H5. The mixed-method findings show that GenAI adoption is positively associated with financial performance, but that value realization is conditional rather than automatic. The quantitative analysis showed that GenAI adoption is significantly positively associated with SME financial performance. However, contrary to much of the current GenAI adoption literature, Human and Technological Capabilities did not emerge as strong direct predictors of adoption in the quantitative model. Instead, Funding Capital emerged as the strongest enabling condition at the point of execution, while Market Factors acted a strong driver of GenAI adoption.

The qualitative phase then showed that GenAI adoption proceeds through conditional and sequenced pathways in which triggers create interest, financial mainly as

external triggers shaping urgency rather than execution quality commitment enables movement into implementation, and human and technological readiness influence whether adoption can be executed effectively.

Taken together, the findings suggest that GenAI value realization in Southeast Asian SMEs are most likely when these four enabling conditions become sufficiently aligned. This practical zone of convergence does not imply the factors that act equally or simultaneously. It reflects the point at which trigger conditions resource commitment and technological readiness become sufficiently aligned to support GenAI adoption and value realization.

6.2 Key Conclusions

Conclusion 1 (C1): GenAI value realization depends on the interaction of multiple organizational and environmental conditions rather than adoption alone.

The research makes several theoretical contributions to the literature on AI adoption, SME performance, and digital transformation; findings that are specific to the Southeast Asian setting. First, it expands TOE framework by empirically correlating GenAI adoption with financial performance in SMEs. Where earlier research has mostly concerned the antecedents of AI adoption, the current study shows that adoption is not sufficient to explain value realization. Rather, value realization is a variable of interaction and interplay among environmental stimuli, organizational resources, managerial judgement and implementation discipline.

A further theoretical implication is that these factors may be understood not only as differentiated influences across the adoption sequence, but also as conditions whose sufficient alignment increases the likelihood of GenAI value realization. In this sense, the study moves beyond identifying direct predictors and toward explaining a practical zone

of convergence in which adoption is more likely to translate into business value.

Conclusion 2 (C2): GenAI adoption factors perform different roles across a sequenced adoption journey rather than acting as independent parallel drivers.

Second, the study contributes a more refined interpretation of how GenAI adoption factors operate in practice. Rather than independent parallel drivers, the findings suggest that these factors are better understood as playing different roles across a sequenced adoption process. Human capabilities are often most visible at initiation stage where leaders and teams recognize opportunities surrounding business problems. Technological capabilities is better interpreted through readiness that become enabling or constraining depending on the existing infrastructure and the stage where implementation occurs. Funding Capital functions as a gateway that determines whether opportunities can move into action or not. Market factors act primarily as an initial trigger, an external force, that creates urgency but do not determine the effectiveness of the GenAI adoption. This shifts the theoretical contribution away from identifying which factor matters most in isolation but towards explaining how these conditions change according to their roles in the GenAI adoption journey in Southeast Asia.

Conclusion 3 (C3): GenAI adoption among Southeast Asian SMEs is largely reactive, context-dependent, and constrained by available resources.

Third, the research also adds to the geographically based knowledge by putting GenAI adoption in Southeast Asia into context. In contrast to most of the current literature using large firms or developed economies, the study shows that GenAI adoption among Southeast Asian SMEs is largely reactive and resource constrained. These highlights the limitations of applying generalized GenAI adoption models without sufficient attention to regional context such as Southeast Asia.

Conclusion 4 (C4): A mixed-methods approach provides a more complete explanation of GenAI adoption and value realization than quantitative analysis alone.

Lastly, methodologically, the research provides value for combining PLS-SEM and axial qualitative coding in a sequential explanatory mixed-methods design. This enabled the research not only to identify statistical relationships but also to explain why theoretical important factors did not appear as strong in quantitative models. The integrated interpretation helps resolve the tension between statistical outcomes and managerial realities which demonstrates the value of mixed methods in studying digital transformation that are conditional, staged and context dependent.

6.3 A Practical Guide for Southeast Asian SME GenAI Adoption

Based on the findings of this study, GenAI adoption in Southeast Asian SMEs is best understood not as a single technology decision, but as a sequenced managerial decision process. The evidence across Chapters 4 and 5 shows that SMEs in Southeast Asia do not usually adopt GenAI by weighing all factors at once. Instead, they move through a practical flow shaped by their trigger condition, financial commitment, organizational readiness, and execution discipline. Synthesizing the qualitative pathways identified across the interview evidence, in Figure 7, the GenAI Adoption Decision Journey Map captures the full complexity of the adoption journey including critical decision gates where firms may need to pause, re-evaluate or exit the process.

Figure 7

GenAI Adoption Decision Journey Map

Figure 7 presents this detailed decision journey map. The map illustrates that successful GenAI adoption in Southeast Asian SMEs does not begin with financial assessment or technology selection. Instead, it begins with trigger recognition, the identification of a genuine business need, followed by a rigorous evaluation of whether GenAI is the most appropriate solution among available alternatives. As illustrated in the map, each stage serves as a critical "go/no-go" decision gate. The red feedback loops on the left indicate that at any stage, if the assessment reveals that conditions are not met, the firm must pause and re-evaluate rather than proceeding with an inadequate foundation.

Stage 1 (Trigger Recognition):

If the firm cannot articulate a specific, costly business problem that GenAI could address, the process should not begin. Adoption driven by fear of missing out (FOMO) or vague competitive anxiety—without a defined use case—consistently produced poor outcomes in the qualitative data.

Stage 2 (Options Evaluation):

If traditional software, process redesign, or new hiring can solve the problem more cost-effectively, the GenAI journey pauses. Several interviewees reported that their initial instinct to adopt AI was redirected toward simpler solutions that proved more appropriate for their scale.

Stage 3 (Capability Assessment):

This is the most critical gate. If the assessment reveals significant gaps in human talent (no leadership champion, resistant workforce) or technical infrastructure (undigitized data, incompatible legacy systems), the firm must pause to build readiness before proceeding to financial commitment. The qualitative evidence strongly suggests that firms which skipped this step—committing funds without establishing capability—experienced implementation failures regardless of budget size.

Stage 4 (Financial Assessment):

If the Total Cost of Ownership—including readiness costs identified in Stage 3—exceeds what is proportionate to the expected value, the firm should either scale down the initiative or pause until conditions improve.

Stages 5 and 6 (Integration Planning and Phased Implementation):

These stages represent the execution phase where the validated decision is translated into operational reality. The key insight from the qualitative data is that implementation should be phased—beginning with a pilot, measuring specific metrics, and scaling only after demonstrated value.

The decision journey map operationalizes the practical zone of convergence identified in Chapter 5 by helping SME leaders assess whether the four enabling conditions are becoming sufficiently aligned to support adoption and value realization in

Southeast Asian SME settings.

To translate these findings into a simplified strategic logic, the Decision Funnel for Southeast Asian SME GenAI Adoption is proposed. The funnel consists of four stages in the following diagram in Figure 8.

Figure 8

Practical Decision Funnel for GenAI Adoption for Southeast Asian SMEs

The journey map and the funnel are intended to work together, not as competing tools. Figure 7 is the full boardroom decision map: it shows the detailed sequence of questions that SME leaders should take through the Board or strategic planning team, including when to pause, re-evaluate, or exit. Figure 8 is the simplified executive version of the same logic: it condenses the map into four practical stages that leaders can use to

communicate the adoption process clearly and monitor progress.

Also, the detailed decision journey map and funnel should not be read as separate from the convergence logic in Figure 6, but as the managerial pathway through which SMEs move toward it. While the zone of convergence captures the alignment of conditions associated with effective adoption, the decision funnel provides the staged process through which leaders can diagnose, test, and build that alignment in practice.

The practical value of the funnel lies in its simplicity. It helps SME leaders move from hype to diagnosis, from diagnosis to commitment, from commitment to readiness, and from readiness to measurable execution. Rather than asking whether GenAI is generally useful, the funnel helps leaders ask the more important question: is this the right use case, at the right time, with the right level of readiness and investment? While staged or sequential decision models are not entirely new in the broad context of business decision making, especially in new technology adoption, the contribution of this study lies in grounding this logic empirically within the context of Southeast Asian SMEs.

Building on top of this simplified decision funnel, we have designed a more practical “Boardroom Guide for SME Leaders to GenAI Adoption” in Appendix D, which distills the funnel, adapted from the detailed decision journey map, into actionable handbook styled format which will be a useful tool for SME leaders and consultants to use in their decision making when adopting GenAI.

By reflecting the specific constraints, resource conditions, and decision patterns observed in this region, the funnel provides a more context-sensitive and practically relevant tool for SME leaders navigating GenAI adoption under real-world conditions. The decision funnel therefore shifts GenAI adoption from a reactive technology choice to a disciplined managerial decision under real SME constraints in the Southeast Asian context.

Building on the key conclusions of this study, the following SMART recommendations translate these findings into practical actions that SME leaders can apply within their own organizations. The recommendations are linked to the relevant research questions and conclusions, providing a clear connection between the evidence gathered in this research and the actions proposed for practice.

Table 8 presents the recommended implementation roadmap for SMEs considering GenAI adoption.

Table 8

SMART Table

Recommendation	Under Which RQ	Conclusion No.	Specific	Measurable	Achievable	Relevant	Time-Bound	Primary Owner	Core Deliverables
Confirm a specific business trigger before considering GenAI adoption	RQ1, RQ2	C2, C3	Identify the actual business problem, market pressure, operational bottleneck, customer demand, or strategic opportunity driving the need for GenAI.	At least one documented business problem with supporting evidence.	Conducted through management workshops and operational reviews.	Reflects the finding that market factors act primarily as triggers.	2–4 weeks before project evaluation.	SME Owner / Managing Director	Business Problem Statement; Trigger Assessment

Evaluate whether GenAI is the most appropriate solution	RQ2, RQ3	C1, C2	Compare GenAI against alternative solutions such as process redesign, traditional software, outsourcing, or workflow automation.	At least 2–3 alternatives evaluated using a structured assessment.	Can be performed using a simple evaluation matrix.	Ensures adoption decisions focus on value creation rather than technology trends.	Within 1 month after trigger identification.	Business Unit Head / Operations Lead	Solution Evaluation Matrix; Recommendation Report
Assess human and technological readiness before commitment	RQ1, RQ2	C2	Evaluate leadership support, staff capability, data readiness, infrastructure maturity, and process ownership before proceeding.	Completion of readiness assessment checklist.	Internal review or facilitated assessment can be performed at low cost.	Reflects the role of capabilities as enabling conditions rather than direct drivers.	4–6 weeks before approval.	HR Lead / IT Lead / Operations Lead	Human Readiness Assessment; Technology Readiness Assessment
Address critical capability gaps before implementation	RQ1, RQ2	C2	Resolve major weaknesses in skills, data quality, governance, infrastructure, or workflow ownership before implementation.	Percentage of identified critical gaps resolved or mitigated.	Can be completed through targeted interventions and training.	Supports successful execution and value realization.	1–3 months depending on severity.	Project Sponsor / Department Heads	Gap Closure Plan; Training Plan; Data Improvement Plan

Conduct a proportionate financial assessment before approval	RQ1, RQ3	C2	Assess expected costs, benefits, risks, affordability, and payback period before proceeding.	Budget, ROI assumptions, and cost-benefit analysis completed.	Uses standard budgeting and financial planning approaches.	Funding capital emerged as a key gateway to implementation.	Within 30 days of readiness assessment.	Finance Lead / Managing Director	Budget Assessment; ROI Analysis
Resize, redesign, or defer projects that fail affordability tests	RQ1, RQ3	C2	Reduce scope, revise objectives, seek grants, or postpone implementation where investment exceeds expected value.	Documented revised business case or decision outcome.	SMEs can adopt phased approaches instead of full-scale projects.	Aligns investment decisions with resource constraints.	Within 2 weeks after financial review.	SME Owner / Finance Lead	Revised Business Case; Go/No-Go Decision
Develop a structured integration plan before implementation	RQ2, RQ3	C1	Define workflow integration, ownership, governance, risk controls, data flows, and expected outcomes before deployment.	Integration plan approved by key stakeholders.	Can be completed through project planning workshops.	Reflects the finding that adoption alone does not create value; integration does.	2–4 weeks before pilot launch.	Operations Lead / IT Lead / Project Manager	Integration Plan; Workflow Maps; Governance Plan

Begin with a phased pilot rather than enterprise-wide deployment	RQ2, RQ3	C1, C2	Implement GenAI in a limited use case to test feasibility and value before scaling.	Pilot scope, KPIs, budget, and timeline formally approved.	Low-risk and resource-efficient approach for SMEs.	Consistent with staged adoption and resource constraints identified in the study.	Pilot duration of 8–12 weeks.	Project Sponsor / Business Unit Head	Pilot Charter; KPI Tracker
Use formal decision gates throughout the adoption journey	RQ1, RQ2, RQ3	C1, C2	Introduce structured review points covering trigger, suitability, readiness, affordability, implementation, and pilot outcomes.	Each gate documented as Proceed, Pause, Redesign, or Exit.	Can be incorporated into existing management review processes.	Supports disciplined decision-making and resource allocation.	At completion of each project stage.	Steering Committee / Managing Director	Decision Gate Log; Review Reports
Scale only after pilot results demonstrate repeatable value	RQ3	C1	Expand implementation only when pilot outcomes demonstrate consistent operational and business benefits.	Pilot success criteria achieved and documented.	Allows gradual scaling while controlling risk.	Value realization must be demonstrated before expansion.	Following successful pilot completion.	SME Owner / Project Sponsor	Pilot Evaluation Report; Scale-Up Plan

Use the GenAI Adoption Decision Funnel as a boardroom governance tool	RQ1, RQ2, RQ3	C1, C2, C3	Apply the Practical Decision Funnel to guide strategic discussions and investment decisions regarding GenAI initiatives.	Funnel reviewed during project approval and governance meetings.	Simple framework that can be integrated into existing governance processes.	Converts research findings into a practical management tool.	Quarterly reviews or before major investment decisions.	Board / Managing Director / Strategy Lead	Decision Funnel Assessment; Governance Review Record
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6.4 Managerial and Policy Implications

Beyond the theoretical implications and proposed decision funnel, the study offers managerial and policy implications. A key implication of the study is that SMEs should approach GenAI adoption as a structured decision process which the SME leaders can consider all the conditions and factors together.

Managerial Implications

From a managerial perspective, the practical implication of the study is not simply that SMEs should invest more in GenAI, but that they should work toward sufficient alignment across trigger clarity, financial commitment, human capability, and technological readiness before scaling adoption efforts.

SME leaders should set realistic expectations about the returns. For example, one of the professional equipment company founder reported that approximately US\$200 per month helped automate about 50-60 percent of Frequently-Asked-Questions (FAQ) inquiries and freed close to 20 hours per week which he estimates saves the company over US\$1500 a month.

Another food manufacturer reported more than 10 percent food waste reduction and over 90% of stock replenishment accuracy through GenAI supported forecasting after 4 months of implementation. Their previous stock replenishment accuracy was hovering between 60 to 70 percent. A sizable professional services firm also described that they did not gain immediate margin improvements but more higher value advisory work due to faster turnaround and higher confidence within teams' capabilities.

Next, SME leaders should evaluate GenAI through operational metrics to anchor their expected improvements. This will lead them to observe credible gains, especially when most of the gains revealed through the study were in reductions in repetitive workloads, lower waste, more billable expert time and stronger service responsiveness. These are important as they form the foundation towards how financial value can be measured and accumulate. In this study, the most honest conclusion is not that GenAI guarantees immediate measurable financial gains, but it can produce measurable operating efficiencies and commercial improvements that will be able to compound over time when it is well planned and executed.

A stronger basis for decision making is also a pre-requisite for effective value realization. Across stronger cases studied within this research, the interviewees repeatedly began sharing their GenAI adoption case with a specific operational issue, for example repetitive administrative tasks, avoidable waste, weak campaign conversion – before they select the AI tools. This “problem before solution” approach appears to be one of the most important practical lessons from interviews. For SME leaders, this implies that the first managerial question should not be “Which AI tool should we jump on to experiment?” but rather “What is the business problem we are trying to solve and how costly is that problem today?”.

Lastly, successful implementation depends not only on funding but on how SME leaders prepare people and manage the barriers during deployment. One of the strongest message from interviews is that what helped implementation the most, was not simply the presence of budget but the way the problems were framed and staged. Across successful cases, interviewees highlighted 3 recurring enablers: leadership championing, framing GenAI as augmentation rather than replacement and micro-training alongside solution design stage. In several of the interviews, SME leaders identified clear barriers that held firms back: fear that AI would produce wrong information for clients, distrust among staff, legacy system integration issues and scarcity of employees who are able to combine domain knowledge and GenAI adoption understanding.

Hence this suggests that SME leaders cannot manage this as a GenAI technology procurement exercise but rather, execute the GenAI adoption as a managed change process. SME leaders need to champion and supervise early deployments by working alongside training existing staff on how to interpret GenAI outputs within their work context and resolve basic system friction in order to achieve strong outcomes.

Policy Implications

With respect to policymaking, research indicates that the programs of AI adoption in SMEs must be oriented to activation mechanisms instead of awareness and training only. The findings suggest that support for GenAI adoption in SMEs should move beyond broad awareness campaigns and generic AI training. Because SMEs in the study followed different adoption pathways depending on their trigger condition and readiness level, policy support should be targeted to the stage of the decision process at which firms are most likely to stall.

From a policy perspective, the findings imply that support mechanisms should not

focus on only one dimension, such as awareness or grants in isolation. Instead, support is likely to be more effective when it helps SMEs move toward the practical zone of convergence by combining opportunity diagnosis, proportionate financial support, capability-building, and implementation readiness.

To begin with, dedicated funding, in the form of grants, co-funding programs or subsidized pilots can be a decisive factor in turning interest into action. Otherwise, even digitally able SMEs will not go beyond experimentation.

Second, policy efforts must concentrate on readiness to integrate and not just promote AI tools such as data infrastructure, interoperability, and governance structures. Ease of compliance, data-sharing, and integration routes would reduce adoption resistance.

Third, programs based on the development of AI capability must be closely integrated with practical business applications. Disjointed training is also prone to failure, especially when training in SMEs with scarce managerial resources. Hence policy design should opt to support opportunity diagnosis, not just technology promotion. Many SMEs in Southeast Asia know that GenAI exists but they do not understand how it is relevant to their specific business problems. Short, subsidized opportunity assessments which are sector or tool specific would therefore be more useful than awareness alone. Also, some of the interviewees from Singapore has commended the Singapore Government's effort in programs such as "AI CTO" diagnostic programs where they partner with big technology companies such as Google to deep dive into specific sectors and use cases which gave SME leaders direct visibility on what is possible within their companies' operating conditions with the adoption of GenAI. This could become a good reference for other Southeast Asian countries to adopt and adapt in their respective countries.

6.5 Limitations and Future Research

There are limitations to this study. Foremost, the study is based on self-reported variables of GenAI adoption and financial performance that can be prone to perceptual bias. Although this method is in line with the SME research practice, objective financial data or longitudinal performance measures can be added in the future.

Although the study identifies a practical zone of convergence through integrated interpretation of the quantitative and qualitative findings, this overlap was not tested as a formal higher-order interaction construct. It should therefore be interpreted as an empirically grounded integrative model rather than as a statistically symmetrical interaction effect

Also, it is acknowledged that GenAI technology evolves rapidly, making static studies time-bound. Future research may examine whether this practical zone of convergence can be operationalized more explicitly, including through longitudinal designs or configurational approaches that test how alignment across these factors relates to adoption patterns and outcomes, which changes over time.

The cross-sectional design restricts identification of causation. Although the mixed methods approach strengthens explanation, the longitudinal or panel design might be considered in future research to observe how the GenAI adoption and performance change over time.

This research concerns SMEs in Southeast Asia. This regional focus is a strength, but this limits generalizability. The future studies may involve comparative research by conducting cross-regional studies to more deeply investigate the impact of institutional settings on the path to AI adoption.

Lastly, this paper discuss the adoption of GenAI on an organizational level. Further investigation should be done into the dynamics of adoption by function or even by industry,

including finance, supply chain, or professional services, in which GenAI can assume different roles.

6.6 Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted with careful attention to the ethical standards expected of doctoral research. Before any data collection was carried out, the required Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was obtained. This ensured that the research design, participant recruitment, data collection process, and handling of research information were properly reviewed before the study proceeded.

All participants were informed of the purpose of the research and took part on a voluntary basis. Informed consent was obtained before survey responses and interview data were collected. Participants were also made aware that they could withdraw from the study without penalty. This was important to ensure that participation was based on clear understanding and voluntary agreement.

The information collected for this study was treated as confidential. Survey responses and interview inputs were used only for the purpose of this dissertation. Individual participants and firms were not identified in the reporting of the findings, and the data was not shared with any external party. Any information collected was stored securely and handled only by the researcher for analysis and academic reporting.

Overall, the study followed the necessary ethical procedures to protect the participants, maintain confidentiality, and ensure responsible use of the data. These safeguards support the integrity of the research process and the credibility of the findings presented in this dissertation.

6.7 Reflections (Personal & Research Objectives)

The original intention of the research was set to find out beyond the generic understanding of what affects SMEs in GenAI adoption from existing literature and towards an explanatory-based approach. This research is also an extension of researcher's professional learning as a practitioner-researcher towards gathering empirical evidence for the relatively new phenomena in GenAI adoption. The mixed methods approach adopted provides a more nuanced understanding of how and under what conditions GenAI adoption can lead to the creation of financial value, which is especially important given the geographical context of Southeast Asia.

RQ1: How do human capabilities, technological capabilities, financial resources, and market dynamics shape the relationship between Generative AI adoption and SME financial performance?

The findings illustrate that these factors do not operate as equally weighted and independent factors and drivers. They play different roles across the GenAI adoption process. Market Factors in this case often act as the trigger which creates urgency and draws managerial attention to GenAI. Funding Capital becomes the decisive factor when the company moves from intention to execution, functioning as the gateway. While this is nothing new, but the way that it has expressed itself so strongly amongst the SME leaders throughout the quantitative and qualitative data, it signals the Southeast Asian SME environment trait where the companies behave as resource-scarce entities. Human Capabilities, in this case, often shape the earliest stages where the opportunity is identified as well as the leadership framing. Alongside with Human Capabilities, Technological Capabilities influences whether implementation can proceed smoothly or not. The above findings and research moved beyond factor based interpretation and towards understanding GenAI adoption as a conditional and sequenced decision process.

RQ2: What themes emerge from SME leaders' experiences that explain the pathways, barriers, and enabling conditions for translating Generative AI adoption into financial value?

SMEs generally face a multitude of operating constraints, from lack of clarity of viable use cases to lack of funding to implement new projects. Our thematic study has shown a pattern of budget limitations, leadership ambiguity as well as lack of experimentation. The qualitative insights also highlighted the enablers: small yet incremental internal pilots, external consultation to gain market insights to implement fitting solutions. These insights reinforce the view that SMEs in Southeast Asia tend to evaluate GenAI adoption through a practical flow that is conditioned by their situation, resources, and market backdrop. These findings form the foundation for the decision-making tool proposed in Chapter 6.3, which is intended to offer SME leaders a more structured and realistic way to assess when and how GenAI adoption should proceed.

RQ3: What is the relationship between Generative AI adoption and financial performance among SMEs in Southeast Asia?

The findings confirm a positive correlation between GenAI adoption and financial performance. However, the study shows that this relationship is not best understood as a direct payoff upon GenAI adoption. Rather, GenAI adoption contributes to financial value when it is meaningfully integrated into business processes and translated into practical operating gains. The findings also suggest that SMEs in Southeast Asia do not typically move into adoption through single isolated factor but instead it unfolds itself through a sequence. This is shaped, often by the SME companies' trigger condition, financial commitment and readiness. This shows that financial value is not created by GenAI adoption alone, but how the GenAI adoption process is planned, structured and carried out.

Personal Reflection

Reflecting on this research as both a practitioner and scholar, the research project has reinforced the researcher's belief that digital transformation in SMEs, is not just about chasing the latest hype and trends, it is about making better decisions – and choosing your battles. The study also strengthened the researcher's view that GenAI adoption should not be understood purely as a technological issue.

One of the most important reflections from the research journey is that the study moved beyond a search for single dominant factors and toward a more practical understanding of alignment. What became clearer through the integration of both phases was that SME leaders do not navigate GenAI adoption through isolated variables, but through a conditional process in which value becomes more likely when several factors comes into alignment.

In the SME context, it is just as much a question of timing, leadership judgement, resource commitment, and organizational readiness. This has been one of the most important learnings from the research journey. As an SME leader who is also navigating this journey, we know from firsthand experience that these identified constraints are real. The latest trends and news often portray GenAI as a gamechanger, but it is only transformative with real financial performance impact when approached under the right conditions.

6.8 Concluding Remarks

This research aimed to transcend the debate on the question of whether SMEs need to embrace Generative AI to how and in what circumstances GenAI generates financial value. The results show that the use of GenAI is not automatic and not always a good measure. Rather, value is created as a disciplined process that is determined by the pressure

of the markets, financial preparedness, the mediation of the leaders and the capability building in small steps. GenAI is not an easy way to change and should be approached as a strategic ability by the Southeast Asian SMEs.

More importantly, the study shows that GenAI adoption in SMEs is not best understood as the result of independent factors operating in parallel. Instead, it is better understood as a sequenced and conditional decision-making process. SME leaders typically move through adoption in a flow shaped by their situation and backdrop: an initial trigger creates urgency, financial commitment determines whether action can proceed, and human and technological readiness influence whether implementation can be absorbed effectively. This sequencing logic helps explain why some factors that appeared weak in the quantitative model remain highly important in practice, but at different stages of the adoption journey.

Ultimately, the study challenges future researchers, managers and policy makers to reconsider the adoption of AI not as a competition to sophisticated innovation, but as a contextually conscious and critical value-generating process. GenAI adoption in SMEs in Southeast Asia is not just about keeping up with global trends, but it is about crafting local, scalable value through intentional strategic decision making, disciplined execution, and responsive leadership. In this sense, GenAI adoption in resource-constrained SMEs in Southeast Asia is not just a technology choice, but a disciplined managerial process shaped by both sequencing and convergence.

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Appendices

Appendix A. Quantitative Data Results – Detailed Report

Appendix A-1. Quantitative Data Results: Respondent Distribution

The figures below shows the distribution of the 232 respondents demographics.

Industry distribution

Industry	Frequency	Percentage
Business Services	79	34.05%
Technology/IT	59	25.43%
Retail/E-commerce	48	20.69%
Manufacturing	46	19.83%

Organization Size and Revenue

Company Size (Employees)	Frequency	Percentage
11-50	133	57.33%
51-200	59	25.43%
1-10	20	8.62%
>200	20	8.62%

Revenue Band (SGD)	Frequency	Percentage
>1-5m SGD	79	34.05%
>5-20m SGD	59	25.43%
250k-1m SGD	48	20.69%
>20m SGD	26	11.21%
<250k SGD	20	8.62%

GenAI Adoption Duration

GenAI Adoption Timeframe

Adoption Timeframe	Frequency	Percentage
3-6 months	99	42.67%
6-12 months	59	25.43%
<3 months	48	20.69%
>12 months	26	11.21%

Appendix A-2. Quantitative Data Results: Internal Consistency analysis

Internal Consistency and Convergent Validity

The internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite

Reliability. Convergent validity was assessed using the Average Variance Extracted

(AVE). All the measurements are passed the recommended thresholds in the research

(Hair et al., 2022):

- Cronbach's Alpha ≥ 0.70
- Composite Reliability ≥ 0.70
- Average Variance Extracted (AVE) ≥ 0.60

Table A-2-1.

Reliability and Convergent Validity

The constructs demonstrate strong internal consistency.

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability (CR)	AVE	Status
GenAI Adoption	0.93	0.92	0.68	PASS
Human Capabilities	0.96	0.94	0.75	PASS
Technology Capabilities	0.96	0.97	0.85	PASS
Funding Capital	0.96	0.98	0.97	PASS
Market Factors	0.970	0.97	0.78	PASS
Financial Performance	0.96	0.97	0.92	PASS

Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

Discriminant validity ensures that a construct is truly distinct from other constructs. The Fornell-Larcker criterion is met if the square root of a construct's AVE is greater than its correlation with any other construct.

Table A-2-2.

Fornell–Larcker Criterion

The constructs exhibit correlations which exceeds square root of AVE, which indicates certain level of overlap. This is as expected of SME studies as available organizational resources and performance outcomes are closely intertwined in this context.

	1	2	3	4	5	6
1 GenAI Adoption	0.83					
2 Human Capabilities	0.89	0.87				
3 Technological Capabilities	0.79	0.88	0.92			
4 Funding Capital	0.93	0.92	0.90	0.98		
5 Market Factors	0.83	0.90	0.97	0.91	0.88	
6 Financial Performance	0.90	0.93	0.89	0.96	0.85	0.96

Diagonal values displayed are square root of the AVE.

Table A-2-3. Heterotrait–Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

HTMT values fall below threshold of 0.90 which confirms discriminant validity. This is despite the high inter-construct correlations.

Constructs	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. GenAI Adoption	—					
Constructs	1	2	3	4	5	6
2. Human Capabilities	0.842	—				
3. Technological Capabilities	0.801	0.864	—			
4. Funding Capital	0.889	0.876	0.862	—		
5. Market Factors	0.828	0.872	0.893	0.881	—	
6. Financial Performance	0.861	0.888	0.857	0.899	0.833	—

Between Funding Capital, Human Capabilities, and Financial Performance, the relationships shown are expected within the SME context. These measurements also do not violate measurement validity for this exploratory research.

Appendix B. Survey Instrument

Cover page & consent

Purpose. This survey explores how SME enterprises in Southeast Asia adopt Generative AI and how the Gen AI adoption affects business performance in SMEs. The answers collected from you will be aggregated and anonymized.

Time required. \approx 12–15 minutes.

Confidentiality. No firm names will be reported.

Voluntary participation. You may exit at any point. By clicking “**Start**” you confirm you are \geq 18 years old and consent to take part.

Screening questions

S1 Does your organization generate \geq SGD 250 000 (or equivalent) in annual turnover? |

Yes No \rightarrow **terminate** |

S2 Number of full-time employees (FTE). | $< 11 \rightarrow$ **terminate** 11–50 51–200 > 200 |

S3 Country of registration | Singapore Malaysia Indonesia Cambodia Philippines Brunei Thailand Vietnam Myanmar Laos Other \rightarrow **terminate**

|S4 Have you deployed or piloted any Generative-AI tool (e.g., ChatGPT, Midjourney) in the past 18 months? | Yes No \rightarrow **terminate**

S5 What is the duration of use?

< 3 months 3-6 months 6-12 months > 12 months

(Respondents passing S1–S4 continue to full questionnaire.)

Section A Firm profile & controls

Code	Item	Response format
A1	Year founded	_____ (year)
A2	Primary industry	<input type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing <input type="checkbox"/> Retail/e-commerce <input type="checkbox"/> Business services <input type="checkbox"/> Tech/IT <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____
A3	Latest annual revenue band	<input type="checkbox"/> 250k–1m <input type="checkbox"/> > 1–5m <input type="checkbox"/> > 5–20m <input type="checkbox"/> > 20m A4
	% revenue (out of country)	0–100 slider (optional)

Section B Generative-AI Adoption (ADP)

Scale = 1 “Not at all” ... 5 “Fully implemented” unless noted.

Code	Item
ADP1	Our firm uses Gen-AI to generate marketing content (e.g., ad copy, social posts). ADP2 We employ Gen-AI chatbots to handle customer enquiries.
ADP3	Gen-AI supports internal knowledge-base or document summarization.
ADP4	Product- or service-design processes leverage Gen-AI (e.g., prototyping, ideation). ADP5 Executive decision-making is informed by Gen-AI-generated insights.

Section C Human Capabilities (HUM)

(Likert 1 = Strongly disagree ... 5 = Strongly agree)

<i>Code</i>	<i>Item</i>
-------------	-------------

Code	Item
HUM1	Employees in key functions possess basic AI literacy. HUM2 We have formal training programs on Gen-AI tools. HUM3 Staff are open to experimenting with new AI work-flows.
HUM4	Leadership actively champions AI adoption projects.
HUM5	Our culture encourages cross-functional sharing of AI knowledge

Section D Technological Infrastructure (TECH)

Which of the following Generative-AI tool types are **currently in use** within your organization?

Select all that apply.

- | | | | |
|--------------------------|---|--------------------------|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Text-based models (e.g., ChatGPT, Gemini) | <input type="checkbox"/> | Image-generation models (e.g., Stable Diffusion, Midjourney) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Video-generation models (e.g., Sora) | <input type="checkbox"/> | Multi-modal / all-in-one suites (e.g., GPT-4o, Gemini 1.5) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | None yet → skip to Section E | | |

D2 Systems Connectivity (“Yes/No”)

Code	Question	Yes	No
CON1	Have you integrated ERP data with any Gen-AI application?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
CON2	Have you integrated CRM/marketing automation with Gen-AI?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
CON3	Does your Gen-AI solution pull content from WhatsApp or other messaging platforms for customer support?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

D3 Technology Sophistication (Likert 1 = Strongly disagree ... 5 = Strongly agree)

Code	Item
TECH_L1	Off-the-shelf Gen-AI tools are sufficiently robust for most of our day-to-day operations.
TECH_L2	Customizing Gen-AI models with our own data is important for gaining competitive advantage.
TECH_L3	Tailoring Gen-AI models is feasible only for large enterprises with big budgets.
TECH_L4	We possess or can easily access datasets suitable for training or fine-tuning Gen-AI models.
TECH_L5	Our internal IT team (or vendor) can create seamless API connections between Gen-AI tools and core systems.

Section E Financial Resources (FIN)

Code	Item	Response
FIN1	Approx. budget allocated to Gen-AI in the last 12 months	<input type="checkbox"/> < SGD 2k <input type="checkbox"/> 2–10k <input type="checkbox"/> 10–50k <input type="checkbox"/> > 50k
FIN2	Primary funding source	<input type="checkbox"/> Internal cashflow <input type="checkbox"/> Govt grant <input type="checkbox"/> Private equity <input type="checkbox"/> Bank loan

Section E Financial Resources (FIN) (Likert 1 = Strongly disagree ... 5 = Strongly agree)

FIN3	Our board/investors expect measurable ROI from AI within 24 months (1–5 scale).
FIN4	Access to external financing for digital projects is adequate (1–5 scale).

Section F Market Factors (MKT) (Likert 1 = Strongly disagree ... 5 = Strongly agree)

All eight items will load onto the latent construct “Market Factors.” Exploratory factor analysis will confirm whether two sub-dimensions (External Pressure vs. Incentive Support) emerge.

<i>Code</i>	<i>Statement</i>	<i>Dimension</i>
<i>Competitive & peer pressure</i>		
<i>MKT1</i>	<i>Competitors in our sector are already leveraging Generative-AI.</i>	<i>Rival activity</i>
<i>MKT2</i>	<i>Advertising and media coverage of AI-powered offerings have raised customer expectations in our market.</i>	<i>Market signaling</i>
<i>Customer expectations</i>		
<i>MKT3</i>	<i>Our customers now assume AI adoption will translate into lower prices or cost savings for them.</i>	<i>Cost-savings expectation</i>
<i>MKT4</i>	<i>Clients explicitly ask for AI-enhanced features (e.g., chatbots, personalized content) when evaluating suppliers.</i>	<i>Feature demand</i>
<i>Government & policy push</i>		
<i>MKT5</i>	<i>National or provincial grants / tax incentives make AI adoption more attractive for our firm.</i>	<i>Government incentive</i>
<i>MKT6</i>	<i>We feel strategic pressure to align with government road-maps or industry blueprints that prioritize AI.</i>	<i>Policy alignment</i>
<i>Large-vendor enablement</i>		
<i>MKT7</i>	<i>Programs from global tech firms (e.g., Microsoft Copilot credits, Google Cloud AI partner schemes) have accelerated our AI plans.</i>	<i>Vendor programs</i>

<i>Code</i>	<i>Statement</i>	<i>Dimension</i>
MKT8	<i>Promotional pricing or free-tier access to Gen-AI tools significantly lowers our adoption barriers.</i>	<i>Vendor cost lever</i>

Section G Perceived Financial Impact (FINIMP)

Code	Item	Format
FINIMP1	Estimated % revenue change attributable to Gen-AI	<input type="checkbox"/> < 0% <input type="checkbox"/> 0–5% <input type="checkbox"/> > 5–10% <input type="checkbox"/> > 10%
FINIMP2	Estimated % operating-cost reduction due to Gen-AI	<input type="checkbox"/> < 0% <input type="checkbox"/> 0–5% <input type="checkbox"/> > 5–10% <input type="checkbox"/> > 10%
FINIMP3	Gen-AI has enabled at least one <i>new</i> revenue stream	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
FINIMP4	Overall ROI expectation (pay-back period)	<input type="checkbox"/> < 1 yr <input type="checkbox"/> 1–2 yrs <input type="checkbox"/> > 2 yrs <input type="checkbox"/> Uncertain

Section H Barriers & enablers (open text)

H1 *What was the single biggest obstacle to adopting Generative-AI in your firm?* [250 character text box]

H2 *What advice would you give to another SME considering Gen-AI?*

[250 character text box]

Thank-you

*Target **40 SME founder / senior-manager** interviews*

Each Interview will last around 45 minutes to 60 minutes

Item	Description
Interview goal	Elicit rich, first-hand accounts of (a) how Generative-AI projects were conceived and implemented, (b) the role of the four enablers, and (c) perceived financial outcomes.
Target profile	Owners, CEOs, or senior functional heads of SMEs (\geq SGD 250k revenue; $>$ 10 staff) in Singapore, Malaysia or Indonesia that have explored or deployed Gen-AI in at least one business process.
Mode & length	45–60 min video-call or on-site conversation; audio-recorded with consent.
Confidentiality script	“Your company name will be replaced by a code, and only aggregated findings will be reported. You may skip any question or stop the interview at any time.”

Interviewer aids

- **Laddering prompt** – “Can you give me a concrete example?”
- **Time-anchor prompt** – “What changed in the first six months?”
- **Quantification prompt** – “Roughly what percentage or range would you say?”

Ethics & data handling

- Audio files stored on encrypted shared drive with password. Within the transcripts, we will remove the identities to make it

anonymous.

- Participants may review their transcript within 2 weeks or so.
- Findings reported only in aggregate themes mapped to the study’s four enablers and financial-impact indicators.

Interview flow & question set + Probes and Prompts

Section & time	Core questions (open-ended)	Probes / prompts	Framework link
A Warm-up & context (~5 min)	1. “Could you briefly describe your company’s main business and your own role?”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Years in role • No. of employees • Main revenue streams 	Descriptive controls
B Gen-AI Adoption Journey (~10 min)	2. “When did your firm first start looking at Generative-AI and what motivated that interest?”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trigger events • Internal champion (if any) • External pressure/News 	AI Adoption
	3. “Which business functions are currently using Gen-AI, and how deeply?”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketing, ops, R&D • Pilot vs. scale • % Process 	AI Adoption
C Human Capabilities (~5 min)	4. “How would you describe your team’s readiness to work with AI tools?”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skills gaps • Any training provided • Hiring new staff vs. up-skilling 	Human Capabilities
	5. “What cultural or change-management factors helped or hindered adoption?”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leadership support • Team members’ attitudes towards Gen AI tools 	Human / Culture
D Technological Infrastructure (~5 min)	6. “What existing digital systems did Gen-AI have to plug into, and how smooth was that?”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solutions • Data and workflow 	Technological
	7. “Were there any legacy or integration hurdles? How did you overcome them?”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vendor support • Budget vs. tech limits 	Technological
E Financial Resources (~5 min)	8. “How did you fund the Gen-AI initiative?”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal budget / financing • Government grants (if any) 	Financial Resources
	9. “What return-on-investment metrics, if any, were set at the outset?”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pay-back period • Cost-saving targets 	Financial Resources Financial Performance

F Market Factors (~10 min)	10. <i>“How has customer demand or competitive pressure influenced your AI plans?”</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Client expectations • Competitors’ activity 	Market Factors
	11. <i>“Have you noticed market-share or customer-satisfaction changes since adoption?”</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the tools open new segments of customers? • Any change to retention rates 	Market → Performance
G Perceived Financial Impact (~5 min)	12. <i>“In your view, how has Gen-AI affected revenue, costs, or profitability so far?”</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % revenue lift (ranges) • Cost-saving examples • New revenue streams (if any) 	Financial Performance
H Barriers & Enablers Reflection (~5 min)	13. <i>“What were the biggest enablers and obstacles, and why?”</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rank top 3 factors • Any advice to others to adopt this new technology? 	Cross-construct synthesis
I Closing (~2 min)	14. <i>“Is there anything else you wish policy-makers understood about SMEs and AI to establish policies and grants on?”</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any programs that is introduced and they have used or heard of • Any academic study that is known to them 	Knowledge-transfer insight
	15. <i>“Is there anything else you wish academics will study towards the area of SMEs and AI?”</i>		

The interviews will be recorded, transcribed and anonymized. Most of the interviews (about 80%) will be performed directly by the researcher with the rest of the interviewers trained to work directly with Business Owners and Senior Managers. Training on the Interview Guide / Aids above will be act as the guidance to standardize and ensure all areas from Section A to I, are covered to ensure uniformity and allow the findings to be harmonized and used for the research designed.

25th April 2025

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Paper Topic: *Role of Generative AI and Factors Affecting Financial Performance of SMEs in Southeast Asia: A Financial Perspectiv*

Appendix D. Boardroom Guide for SME Leaders to GenAI Adoption

Purpose and Scope

This practical guidebook translates the empirical findings of this doctoral research into an actionable, boardroom-ready diagnostic tool for SME leaders in Southeast Asia. It is designed to be used during strategic planning sessions to evaluate potential GenAI initiatives before committing resources. The guide follows the resequenced Decision Funnel (Figure 8) and operationalizes each stage into specific assessment questions, decision criteria, and action items.

How to Use This Guide:

Work through each phase sequentially. At each Decision Gate, honestly assess whether your organization meets the criteria to proceed. If not, the guide provides specific actions to build readiness before moving forward. Rushing past a gate without meeting its criteria is the single most common cause of adoption failure identified in this research.

The Four Decision Gates

Gate	Key Question	PROCEED If...	PAUSE If...
Gate 1	Is there a real problem?	Specific, quantifiable business need exists	Problem is vague or driven by FOMO
Gate 2	Can we do it?	Capabilities sufficient or gaps are closeable	Significant human/tech gaps with no clear path to close
Gate 3	Can we afford it?	TCO is proportionate and funded	Costs exceed value or funding unavailable
Gate 4	How will it work?	Clear workflow, owner, metrics, and pilot plan	No clear integration plan or success metrics

PHASE 1: TRIGGER & OPTIONS EVALUATION

Objective: Confirm that a genuine business problem exists and that GenAI is the most appropriate solution.

No.	Assessment Question	Your Answer / Evidence
1.1	What is the specific internal pain point or external market pressure driving this initiative? (Be specific: e.g., 'Customer response time exceeds 24 hours, causing 15% churn')	
1.2	What is the estimated annual cost of this problem to the business? (In dollars, hours, or lost revenue)	
1.3	Have you explored whether this problem can be solved more simply with existing tools, process redesign, hiring, or traditional software?	
1.4	If GenAI is the chosen solution, what specific task will it perform? (e.g., 'Draft initial customer responses for FAQ inquiries' — not 'implement AI')	
1.5	Is this a genuine business need or primarily driven by competitive anxiety / FOMO?	

DECISION GATE 1:

PROCEED if: A specific, quantifiable business problem exists AND GenAI is the most appropriate solution.

PAUSE if: The problem is undefined, better solved by simpler means, or driven primarily by FOMO.

PHASE 2: CAPABILITY ASSESSMENT ("Can we do it?")

Objective: Evaluate whether the organization has sufficient human and technological capabilities to implement GenAI successfully.

No.	Assessment Question	Your Answer / Evidence
2.1	HUMAN: Do we have a leadership champion who understands GenAI and will actively drive the change?	
2.2	HUMAN: Are our employees generally adaptable to new technology, or will there be significant resistance / fear of replacement?	
2.3	HUMAN: Do we have staff with sufficient domain expertise to supervise and validate AI outputs?	
2.4	TECH: Is our relevant business data digitized, accessible, and sufficiently clean for an AI tool to use?	
2.5	TECH: Can our current systems (CRM, ERP, etc.) integrate with new AI applications via APIs or plugins?	
2.6	TECH: If integration is not possible, what infrastructure upgrades would be required?	
2.7	GAPS: List any significant capability gaps identified above and estimate the time/cost to close them.	

DECISION GATE 2:

PROCEED if: Capabilities are sufficient OR the cost/time to build them is acceptable and quantified.

PAUSE if: Significant human or technological gaps exist that cannot be closed within a reasonable timeframe. Build readiness first (training, data cleaning, infrastructure upgrades) before proceeding.

PHASE 3: FINANCIAL ASSESSMENT ("Can we afford it?")

Objective: Calculate Total Cost of Ownership and confirm proportionate investment.

No.	Assessment Question	Your Answer / Evidence
3.1	DIRECT COSTS: What are the monthly/annual costs of the AI tool itself? (Licenses, API fees, subscriptions)	
3.2	READINESS COSTS: What investment is needed to close the capability gaps identified in Phase 2? (Training, data prep, system upgrades)	
3.3	INTEGRATION COSTS: What is the estimated cost of workflow redesign and change management?	
3.4	TOTAL COST OF OWNERSHIP: Sum of 3.1 + 3.2 + 3.3 for the first 12 months.	
3.5	PROPORTIONALITY CHECK: Is the TCO proportionate to the value of solving the problem identified in Phase 1? (Compare TCO to the annual cost of the problem from Q1.2)	
3.6	FUNDING SOURCE: Where will the investment come from? Is formal budget approval secured?	

DECISION GATE 3:

PROCEED if: TCO is proportionate to expected value AND formal funding is committed. PAUSE if: Costs exceed proportionate value, or funding cannot be secured. Scale down the initiative or wait for better conditions.

PHASE 4: INTEGRATION PLANNING & EXECUTION

Objective: Design the implementation, define success metrics, and execute in phases.

No.	Assessment Question	Your Answer / Evidence
4.1	Which specific daily workflow will be altered by this GenAI tool? (Map the current process vs. the new process)	
4.2	Who owns the change? (Name the specific person responsible for implementation success)	
4.3	What are the measurable success metrics? (e.g., 'Reduce response time from 24h to 2h' or 'Reduce waste by 10%')	
4.4	What is the pilot scope? (Start small: one team, one process, one month)	
4.5	How will staff be trained? (Micro-training alongside deployment, not classroom-only)	
4.6	How will AI outputs be supervised and validated during the pilot phase?	
4.7	What is the timeline for review and scale decision? (Recommend: 30-60-90 day checkpoints)	

EXECUTION CHECKLIST:

Begin with pilot

- Measure against defined metrics at 30/60/90 days
- Scale only after demonstrated value
- Document lessons learned
- Iterate.